

Classical Tibetan Annotation Manual

Part II - Segmentation & POS tagging

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This annotation manual is meant to support annotators in correcting both automatic **word** and **sentence segmentation** as well as **morphosyntactic** (Part-of-Speech) information. It is not meant to be read from cover-to-cover. Rather, it is meant as a document that is easy to navigate to search for examples of cases where annotators are unsure about which decision to take. It has detailed examples of all conventions for segmentation and POS tagging, as well as brief explanations of why certain decisions were made. Unless indicated otherwise in the manual, final decisions on annotation are based on the following principles:

- **linguistically accurate & theory-neutral**: we aim for the most practical description, without analysing the example, so that researchers can find the data they need and do their own analysis in whatever framework they like;
- **pragmatic annotation**: we try to avoid interpreting or analysing ambiguous structures, if such cases arise we go for more generic annotations instead of more detail;
- **UD conversion**: since the UD annotation scheme is not detailed enough for our purposes and also not really suitable for historical corpora in general yet, we use our own, but our POS tags can easily be converted to the UD lemma, POS and morph columns when necessary as our tags are very systematic;
- **word segmentation**: we tend to split in as many meaningful segments as possible to provide more insight into the historical development of the language and to tag as conservatively as possible (following successful examples of this in other historical corpora, e.g. Slavonic (cf. Eckhoff 2022), Welsh (cf. Meelen & Willis 2022), etc.) This means, for example, that case markers and 'converbs' are always cut off and that complex verbal constructions are also separated to be able to give as much morphosyntactic information as possible. Please note that this segmentation protocol says nothing about our ideas about what a 'word' is or should be in Tibetan, it is a purely pragmatic choice to provide the most insightful morphosyntactic annotation that can furthermore aid downstream annotation tasks like parsing;
- **sentence segmentation**: every sentence should have a main predicate (in most cases this will be the main verb): that means there are no utterance boundaries between subordinate and main clauses; if semi-final particles are used to connect two short verbs only, no utterance boundary is added, but usually they are connecting multiple clauses with main predicates in which case each of them is treated as a separate sentence for practical purposes (i.e. to avoid too long sentences that are unwieldy for any downstream NLP task). For the same pragmatic reason, utterance boundaries are added around direct speech and verbs introducing (or ending) direct speech are kept separate (they also received a special syntactic label to make it easier to do research on speech verbs, see Parsing manual).

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1. General Introduction

Our general philosophy with respect to any form of annotation is that it should be descriptive rather than based on analyses to facilitate future research in any area. This general introduction provides examples of our general annotation principles to make annotators and correctors familiar with our general annotation protocols and to provide background regarding annotation decisions. It also gives detailed information about how to deal with verbs in particular. Plenty of examples, some with, some without tags (depending on which source they're from) are given throughout. They are numbered per section.

For **segmentation** we split words as much as possible and we create sentence boundaries between main clauses and with direct speech. See section on [Sentence Segmentation](#). For **POS tagging**, we apply morphological information in a conservative manner to make sure that we can capture the origin of constructions that have changed over time. For example, complex postpositions, as shown here are split and all elements are tagged separately:

(1) སྐང་ལ་ “on top” (see [n.rel section](#))

བུ་ n.count

མཚམས་ n.count

ཏྲི་ case.gen

སྐང་ n.rel

ལ་ case.all

ལྷན་མོ་ n.count

ལ་ case.all

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སྟུ་ p.interrog

མང་ v.pres

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<utt>

1.1 POS Tagging of Verbs

When it comes to verbs, we base our tense-aspect-mood distinctions on morphological form only, i.e. if there is a morphological element that indicates that a verb is past, future or present tense etc. then the verb will be tagged as v.past, v.fut and v.pres respectively. If there is no such morphological information, we don't attempt to analyse and interpret it by putting this information in the tag, but instead, use the more neutral invariant form. Imperative forms that are morphologically distinct from the tense forms are tagged as v.ipv.

(2) “to add together, to combine, to add”

སྒྲིམ་ v.pres

བསྒྲིམས་ v.past

བསྒྲིམ་ v.fut

སྒྲིམས་ v.ipv

However, if the morphology is invariant in all these tenses + the imperative, then the verb will be tagged as v.invar, as illustrated with the verb ལུང་ 'to retreat, to withdraw':

(3) “to retreat, to withdraw”

ལུང་ v.invar (so this can be present, future, past or imperative)

It is possible that another form of the same verb is available, in which case that form will receive the appropriate tag, e.g.

(4) “to manage, provide for”

གཉེར་/v.invar

གཉེར་དེ་/v.past

There are also cases where the morphology is invariant except for the imperative form:

(5) “to smith”

སེལ་ v.invar (so this can be all tense, i.e. present, future or past)

སེལ་བ་ v.ipv

Alternatively, a verb could have the same form for the future and present, but a different form for the past tense, in which case the future/present forms will be tagged as v.fut.v.pres. The past-tense form will then be tagged as v.past. Again imperative forms that are morphologically distinct from the tense forms are tagged as v.ipv.

(6) “to die”

འགྲུམ་ v.fut.v.pres

གྲུམ་ v.past

གྲུམས་ v.ipv

Similarly, there are verbs that have homophonous forms in the future and the past (and optionally the imperative), which will result in a v.fut.v.past tag. This also goes for verbs that share present, future and imperatives.

(7) “to decline, to diminish”

འགྲུད་ v.pres

གྲུད་ v.fut.v.past

(8) གསུང་/v.fut.v.pres

Note that this means that the imperative form is NOT tagged separately for those verbs and can only be derived from the context, e.g. through following imperative markers:

(9)

གུད་/v.fut.v.past ཞེག་/cv.ipv
གསུང་/v.fut.v.pres ཞེག་/cv.ipv

There are also verbs that have homophonous forms in the future, past and present (and optionally the imperative), with also an alternative distinct form for the past.

(10) “to recover from illness”

Present: དྲག་ LZ, DK, DS, TC.

Past: དྲགས་ LZ. དྲག་ DK, [DS], TC.

Future: དྲག་ LZ, DK, [DS], TC.

Imperative: དྲག་ LZ, DK. – TC.

In those cases we indicate with (ipv) that the form also appears in the imperative, but it will result in the following tags:

(11)

དྲག་ → v.invar དྲགས་ → v.past

1.2 Past tense with da-drag

In cases where the past tense is covertly marked through sandhi rules following da-drags, we still tag the verb as v.past. As a consequence, the verbs that don't have this covert past-tense marking will be tagged as v.fut.v.pres instead of v.invar.

(13) “to dispose of the dead”

དུར་ད་/v.past

དུར་/v.past རྩོལ་/cv.fin → v.past because of the sandhi in the final particle starting with d-

དུར་/v.fut.v.pres རྩོལ་/cv.fin → v.fut.v.pres because of the lack of sandhi in the final particle

With frequent special verbs like *yin* this works in the same way:

(14) “to be”

ཡིན་ད་/v.past.yin

ཡིན་/v.past.yin རྩོལ་/cv.fin → v.past because of the sandhi in the final particle starting with d-

ཡིན་/v.fut.v.pres.yin རྩོལ་/cv.fin → v.fut.v.pres because of the lack of sandhi in the final particle

1.3 Special Verbs (see [Special Verb List](#))

Some verbs that exhibit special behaviour (e.g. they can behave like copulas or auxiliaries, etc.) get an individual verbal tag. This effectively means these verbs are lemmatised, making it easy to do research on them. Very often, these are verbs that change into some sort of evidential or epistemic marker in any modern variety. Note that common light verbs are not necessarily specified/tagged separately in this way because no one really has done enough

research on light verbs to make a good list. The choice of which verbs to include is based on what is known about the historical development of the verb, any other linguistic information that may set them apart, and, finally, frequency counts from corpora. Some examples are shown in (15):

(15)

- a. མེད་ → v.invar.red “to be”
- b. མེད་བ་ → n.v.invar.red “to be”
- c. ཡོད་ → v.invar.yod “to exist, to have”
- d. ཡོད་བ་ → n.v.invar.yod “to exist, to have”

1.4 Homophonous Special Verbs

There are cases where the forms of the verbs themselves are homophonous: if the verbs have two different argument structures, then we have two separate verbs and we use two separate tags verb1 "V1" and verb2 "V2":

(16) myong1 “to taste to perceive”, myong2 “to feel, to sense”

- a. མྱོང་ → v.pres.myong1 - always transitive with [Erg. Abs.]
- b. མྱོངས་ → v.past.myong1
- c. མྱོང་ → v.fut.myong1
- d. མྱོང་ → v.invar.myong2 - always intransitive

If Hill’s dictionary doesn’t give two different argument structures AND the [Visual Dictionary of Tibetan Verbs](#) doesn’t give two different argument structures, then we don’t consider them to be two separate verbs. We also do not consider མེད་ to be have two separate verbs (unlike the dictionaries).

1.5 Resultatives & Causatives

If a special verb V1 is resultative/causative of a verb V2 we use the same special verb tag for both.

(17)

- a. འགྱུར་ → v.fut.v.pres.gyur (ipv)
- བསྐྱུར་ → v.fut.v.past
- ལྟུར་ → v.pres.gyur (ipv) - alternative form འགྱུར་
- ལྟུར་ → v.past.gyur - alternative forms ལྟུར་ (ipv); བསྐྱུར་
- ལྟུར་དྲ་ → v.ipv.gyur
- b. འགྱུར་བ་ → n.v.fut.n.v.pres.gyur (ipv)
- བསྐྱུར་བ་ → n.v.fut.n.v.past
- ལྟུར་བ་ → n.v.pres.gyur (ipv) - alternative form འགྱུར་བ་
- ལྟུར་བ་ → n.v.past.gyur ལྟུར་བ་ (ipv) - alternative form བསྐྱུར་བ་
- ལྟུར་དྲ་བ་ → n.v.ipv.gyur
- c. འགྱུར་ is the resultative of ལྟུར་

We added ལྟུར་ to our special verb list and tag all its forms with the same special tag “gyur” we

used for འཕྱུར་ (see above).

There are cases where a verb V1 is in fact the causative of a verb V2. Causative forms are treated as separate forms like any other verb that has two different argument structures.

(18) མྱོལ་ "to obscure, to cover"

Present: མྱོལ་ v.pres

Past: བམྱོལས་ v.past

Future: བམྱོལ་ v.invar

Imperative: མྱོལས་ v.ipv

Causative of: འཕྱིལ་ "to grow dim, to get dark"

Present/Future/Past: འཕྱིལ་ v.invar

Past: མྱིལ་ འཕྱིལས་ v.past

2. Word segmentation

Our main protocol is that case markers and converbs are split from the preceding noun phrases. In general, we split as much as possible to create more insight into the internal (and historical) structure. In what follows, we first present examples of these [case markers](#) (tagged "case.X") and [converbs](#) (tagged "cv.X"), followed by examples of personal names, titles and compounds (see also section on n.count). All data are taken from our training data or other corpora.

2.1 Case markers & converb segmentation

(1)

དེ d.dem

ས་ case.term

པ p.pers

ས་ case.agn

ལྱང་ cl.focus

སྐྱམ་ n.count

འི་ case.gen

བཀའ་ n.count

(2)

ཚུ་མི་ n.prop

འབྲེལ་ v.past.v.pres

ནས་ cv.ela

ཡོད་ v.invar.yod

དྲི་ cv.sem

། punc

2.2 Personal Names and Titles

With personal names, which are tagged as [n.prop](#) ('proper noun'), we split as much as possible to create more insight into the internal structure of the sentence. The same goes for commonly used titles, as shown in (3):

(3) ལྷ་མོ་ཚེ་མོ་ → ལྷ་མོ་/n.count ཚེ་མོ་/adj

(4)

དྲིན་ཅན་ adj

མར་པ་ n.prop

ལོ་རྒྱུ་བ་ n.count

(5)

ལྷོ་ n.count

ལ་ཡག་ n.prop

གི་ case.gen

བ་རང་ n.prop

ལྷ་ཅན་ n.prop

རྣམས་ d.plural

ལགས་ v.invar.lags

སོ་ cv.fin

| punc

(6)

གཙང་ n.prop

ལྷ་ར་ལྷ་ n.prop

འི་ case.gen

ལྷོ་གཙང་ n.prop

ཚེ་མོ་ adj

2.3 Compound nouns

In general, when two nouns occur in succession they are understood as a compound. Since our main principle is to split meaningful segments as much as possible, we have very few compounds. There are a few obvious compounds that we do not split, however, e.g. the dvandva compound མ་མ་ 'parents' is treated as one noun rather than two (མ་ 'father' and མ་ 'mother') and the tatpuruṣa compound འཁྱིམ་བདག་ 'householder' is likewise treated as one noun rather than two (འཁྱིམ་ 'home' and བདག་ 'lord'). When an adjective precedes its head this is also treated as a compound. Thus, because དུག་བཙོན་མོ་ would be the expected order for 'mighty poison', we treat བཙོན་དུག་ 'mighty poison' as a single word. Similarly, གང་ན་བ་ 'whereabouts' and བདག་གི་བ་ 'that which is mine' are single words.

2.4 Complex & light verb constructions

We do not annotate light-verb constructions but we introduce a list of special verbs and verbal nouns that will help researchers to identify such potential constructions later.

(7)

ཚུམ་གྲུ་ n.count
དོ་ d.dem
ལ་ case.all
ཕུག་ n.count
འཚམ་ v.fut.v.pres.tshal1
ལོ་ cv.fin

We furthermore split complex verb constructions as much as possible:

(8)

འིན་ཚེན་ n.count
བདུན་ num.card
ཕྱིས་ case.agn
ཡོངས་ d.plural
སྲུ་ case.term
བཀའ་ v.past
བྱས་ v.past.byed
ནས་ cv.ela
| punc

(9)

གསེར་ n.mass
ལས་ case.abl
བརྗེདས་ v.past
བྱས་ v.past.byed
འདྲ་ v.invar.dra2
ཞིང་ cv.impf
པར་ n.count
རྒྱས་པ་ n.v.past
བཞིན་ n.rel
| punc

(10)

དོན་ n.count
རྣམས་ d.plural
གཉིས་ num.card
ལྡན་ v.invar
གཟུང་ v.fut
སླ་ v.pres
དང་ cv.ass

3. POS tagging

In this section, we go through every single morphosyntactic (part-of-speech) tag and provide

explanations and examples of when they are applied.

3.1 Adjectives

There is only one tag for adjectives: adj. We do not distinguish different types of adjectives or different grades of adjectives. Note that in general, verbs derived from adjectives are tagged (n.)v.invar unless they have -s, in which case they are (n.)v.past (see section on [verbs](#)).

adj - adjectives

Adjectives are notoriously difficult to define in any Sino-Tibetan language. For our annotation purposes, we give the POS tag adj to those words that can occur in attributive position and are not verbal nouns. Morphologically, they are almost always multisyllabic. The paragon of adjectives are those that in -པོ་, -མོ་, -པ་, -མ་, -ཅན་, -ལྗན་, and -མེད་. Etymologically ཅན་, -ལྗན་ 'with', and -མེད་ 'without' are verbs, but when they occur in forms that are functioning nominally, they cannot be analysed as verbs. Therefore, we treat them together with the preceding syllable as an adjective. Although words such as རྒྱུ་ 'black', གསར་ 'new', and ཆེ་ 'big' are frequently treated like adjectives for pedagogical purposes, a single syllable in predicate position before verbal suffixes is tagged as a verb 'to be black', 'to be new', etc. These words may appear to occur attributively, but we see this as the formation of compounds. The compound སློན་ཆེན་ 'prime minister' contrasts beautifully with the noun and adjective pair སློན་པོ་ ཆེན་པོ་ 'great minister', etc.).

There are various cases where homophonous verbs and adjectives may cause ambiguity, making it difficult to decide how to annotate them. We adhere to the following protocols for those cases. First, verbs derived from adjectives are tagged (n.)v.invar, as shown in (1):

- (1)
རྩ་ adv.intense
རྩ་ cv.term
འབྱུང་བ་ n.v.fut.n.v.pres
ར་ case.term
དྲུག་ v.invar → this is tagged as v.invar and not as adj
ལོ་ cv.fin
། punc

Second, sometimes, nominalised forms are actually derived twice, i.e. first from adj → verb and then from verb → verbal noun. An example of this is seen here where རྩ་བ་ can only mean 'the [time of] being small' and not 'the small person'. In those cases, they are tagged as n.v.invar, as shown in (2):

- (2)
རྩ་བ་ n.v.invar → this is left as a double derivation n.v.invar
འི་ case.gen
དུས་ n.rel

ལྷ་ case.term
 ལེན་དྲན་གྱི་ལེན་ n.prop
 ལྷ་ case.loc
 ལྷོ་ལམ་ n.count
 ལྷི་ case.gen
 ལྷོན་ n.count
 ལུགས་པ་ n.v.invar
 ལྷི་ case.gen
 ལྷལ་ n.count
 ལུ་ case.term
 | punc
 <utt>

A similar example is found in (3): 'because his discipline was small, his accomplishments also were few'. Note that the second verbal noun in this example is derived from the verb 'to accomplish', so even though the nominalised form functions as a noun, it will still have the n.v. tag. The issue of n.v. versus n.count tag only arises with adjectives like 'small' → 'to be small' (=verbal) vs 'small person' (=nominal). More examples are given in (4-6) below.

(3)
 ལུང་ལྷོན་ལྷལ་ n.count
 ལུང་ལྷོན་ n.v.invar 'to be small'
 ལྷ་ case.agn
 ལྷལ་པ་ n.v.past 'accomplishment'
 ལང་ cl.focus
 ལུང་ལྷོན་ n.v.past.n.v.pres 'to be small/few'
 ལྷ་ case.term
 ལྷལ་ v.fut.v.pres
 | punc
 <utt>

(4)
 ལྷལ་ལྷོན་ n.count
 ལུང་ལྷོན་ n.v.past
 ལྷ་ case.agn
 ལྷོན་ལྷོན་ n.count
 ལྷལ་ལྷོན་ d.plural
 ལྷི་ case.agn
 ལྷོན་ལྷོན་ n.count
 ལྷོན་ལྷོན་ v.past
 ལྷོན་ cv.sem
 | punc

(5)
 ལྷོན་ n.rel
 ལྷ་ case.term
 ལྷོན་ལྷོན་ n.v.fut.n.v.pres

(7)

མང་པ་ n.prop

ས་ case.agn

མུ་མ་ n.count

གསང་ v.invar

ལྟེ་ cv.sem

| punc

<utt>

case.all

Allative case. The allative case is the clitic morpheme ། -la when it occurs suffixed to nouns, noun phrases or verbal nouns.

(8) རྒྱ་མཐོང་ལ་ལྟོ་ “to look **at** the sky” (MB D 140r5 - Bialek 2022, p.60)

case.all can also mark oblique arguments of certain verbs. For more meanings, and examples see Bialek 2022 pp.59-60. Bialek 2022 argues that when suffixed to a verbal noun ། indicates simultaneity or anteriority with the action of the main verb. She cites the following example that is supposed to be simultaneous (but her translation actually indicates causality), which we also tag as case.all:

(9) ཟས་དེ་ཡོན་ཏན་ཅན་ཞིག་འདུག་པ་ལ། ངས་ཀྱང་ཟ། “As this food is excellent, I will eat [it] too.” (GLR 27r6, Bialek 2022 p.152)

For more examples see Bialek 2022, p.148-149 and p. 152.

case.abl

Ablative case. The ablative case is the morpheme ། -las when it occurs suffixed to nouns, noun phrases or verbal nouns. After nouns, it usually means origin/source:

(10) རྒྱ་མཐོང་ལས་བབས་སོ། “[He] came down from the sky.”
(MB D 140r5 - Bialek 2022, p.91)

The comparative construction use the ablative ། -las as the comparative marker. The morpheme follows the noun/noun phrase which is compared, and the quality (adjective) for which it is compared follows the particle:

(11) བཞུན་ལས་ཆེ་བ་ “bigger (ཆེ་བ་) than the other one” (SBM; apud Schwieger 2006: 315 - Bialek 2022, p.185)

When the morpheme ། follows a verbal noun, it indicates that the action of the converb is anterior to the following action. Even though this is referring to an event (a verb), to be consistent, we tag these examples after verbal nouns as case.abl and not as cv.abl, which only occurs after verbs. If the verb is reduplicated it indicates continuation and it can be

translated with “while”:

- (12) བྱིས་བདག་ཀྱང་གླང་འོངས་པར་མཐོང་བ་ལས་མ་བཏགས་པས་ན། མིག་ཕྱང་ཞིག
 “Because (ལས་ན) the householder, upon (ལས་) seeing that the ox came in, did not bind [it],
 gouge out [his] eyes!” (MB D 272v1)

case.agn

Agentive case. The agentive case is marked by any of the allomorphs གིས་ -*gis*, གྱིས་ -*gyis*, གྱིས་ -*kyis*, ས་ -*s*, ཡིས་ -*yi*s when it occurs suffixed to nouns, noun phrases or verbal nouns. It marks the subject of transitive verbs (we do not make distinctions when its role is more of a “causative case”):

- (13) དེ་ནས་སྤེལ་ཕྱག་རྒྱུ་ལྷོ་ལོ་ཐོག་བོས་སོ། “Then, the monkey-children ate the crops.”
 (GLR 23v4 - Bialek 2022, p.82)

case.ass

Associative case. The associative case is the clitic morpheme དང་ -*dang* when suffixed to nouns, noun phrases or verbal nouns. It has a coordination function - as the conjunction “and”- between two or more nouns or noun phrases. It can mark oblique arguments of certain verbs that express similarity, association, or separation (dissociation).

- (14) ལྷན་པ་དང་མོ་མ་རྒྱམས་ “doctors and diviners” (ML D 10r - Bialek 2022, p.84)

After a nominalised verb དང་ serves to coordinate two syntactically equal clauses with each other. It can be translated as “and”.

- (15) འོག་སྐུམ་འོན་པ་དང་། སྤེལ་བྱ ང་རྒྱལ་སེམས་དཔའ་བཟླར་ཕྱིན་པས།
 “Three years passed and (དང་) the bodhisattva-monkey went to inspect [them].”
 (GLR 23r4. Bialek 2022 p.149)

case.comp

Comparative case. The comparative construction is expressed using the morpheme བས་/བས་. after a noun, noun phrase or verbal noun. Note that this function can also be expressed by the ablative case marker (see [case.abl](#) and Hill 2012).

- (16) གླང་པོ་ཆེ་བས་སྟོབས་ཆེ་བ་ lit. “of greater strength than an elephant”
 (ML D 17r - Bialek 2022, p.186)

For more complex examples see Bialek 2022, p.186.

case.ela

Elative case. The elative case is the clitic morpheme ནས་ *-nas* when suffixed to nouns, noun phrases or verbal nouns. Usually it expresses a place/time from which an action begins or the cause for which an action occurs. It can form adverbs when suffixed to adjectives.

(17) བླ་མཁའ་ནས་ “from the sky” (GLR 22v5 - Bialek 2022. p.90)

For more meanings, and examples see Bialek 2022 pp. 90-91.

case.fin

Sentence-final particle. This is a sentence-final particle that does NOT occur after a verb. Most of the time sentence-final particles occur after verbs and are thus tagged [cv.fin](#). However, they can also appear at the end of the sentence after noun phrases, verbal nouns or other parts of speech, as shown in (18):

(18)

ཡང་ adv.proclausal

ན་ case.loc

ནི་ cl.top

མི་ n.count

འདི་ d.dem

འི་ case.gen

རྒྱུ་མ་ n.count

མངལ་བྱུང་ n.count

ཤིན་ adv.intense

དུ་ cv.term

མཛེས་ v.invar

ཤིང་ cv.impf

བཟང་མོ་ n.count

ཞིག་ d.indef

ལྟོ་ case.fin

| punc

<utt>

case.gen

Genitive case. The genitive case is any of the allomorphs གི་ *-gi*, གྱི་ *-gyi*, གྱི་ *-kyi*, འི་ *-i*, ཡི་ *-yi*, when suffixed to a noun, noun phrase or verbal noun. The main function of the genitive particle is to mark a noun or a noun phrase as possessive, modifying another noun.

(19) རྒྱལ་པོའི་སྲས་གསུམ་ “king’s three sons” (GLR 25r4 - Bialek 2022, p.63)

Note that when a genitive particle is added to a nominalised phrase or clause it forms a relative clause:

(20) ཤིན་དུ་དང་པོ་སེམས་ “a mind that utterly believes” (MB D 138v5, Bialek 2022 p.139)

case.loc

Locative case. The locative case is the clitic morpheme ན་ *-na* when suffixed to a noun, noun phrase or to a verbal noun. It can have temporal or spatial meaning.

(21) གོང་ཁྱེར་དེ་ན་ “in that town” (MB D 138r7 - Bialek 2022, p.58)

ན་ has temporal function when it follows a verbal noun, meaning 'if/when':

It has temporal function when it follows a verbal noun.

(22) ཉི་མའི་འོད་ཟེར་གསལ་བ་ན། འབྲུང་པོའི་བྱ་རྣམས་འོང་བར་འགྱུར། “When rays of the sun have risen, the birds of demons (i.e. owls and other nocturnal birds) become blind.” (SSP 3c–d, Bialek 2022, p.152)

case.nare

The case -na-re. The case suffix ན་རེ་ *-na-re* introduces direct speech.

(23) དྲག་སྲིན་མོ་ན་རེ། བྱེད་ངའི་ཕྱོ་མི་བྱེད་ན་ང་ཚོའི་དུས་བྱེད་དོ་ཟེར་ནས།
“The rock-ogress replied, ‘If you don’t become my husband, I will die.’” (GLR 22r6 - Bialek 2022, p.158)

case.ques

Question particle. Question particles usually follow verbs, but occasionally, they can follow nouns or verbal nouns. These question particles that are NOT following verbs are tagged case.ques (unlike [cv.ques](#)).

(24)

བདག་ p.pers

དེ་ d.dem

ལ་ case.all

ཅུང་ཟད་ adv.intense

ཙམ་ d.tsam

མི་ neg

དགའ་བ་ n.v.fut.n.v.pres

ལས་ case.ques

<utt>

འཁོན་ v.fut.v.pres

དུ་ cv.term

འཛིན་པ་ n.v.pres

མེད་ v.invar.med

དོ་ cv.fin

། punc

<utt>

case.rung

Case marker རྩུང་, རྩུང་ when it is NOT following a verb (unlike [cv.rung](#)).

(25)

འཇམ་གུ་ n.prop
འི་ case.gen
གླིང་ n.count
དབང་ n.count
རྩུང་ case.rung
འཆི་ v.fut.v.pres
ཚེ་ n.rel
བཞག་ v.past.bzhag
དགོས་ v.invar.dgos
འདུག་པ་ n.v.invar.dug
ས་ case.agn
| punc
<utt>

case.sem

Semi-final particle. Just like the sentence-final particle, the semi-final particle usually appears after verbs. However, it can also occur after noun phrases or verbal nouns, in which case it is tagged as case.sem (unlike [cv.sem](#) which occurs after verbs).

(26)

རྒྱལ་པོ་ n.count
གསལ་རྒྱལ་ n.prop
ལྱི་ case.gen
བུ་མོ་ n.count
རྩོམ་ n.count
འི་ case.gen
ལུ་ལྷ་ n.count
ལྟེ་ case.sem
བདུན་པ་ num.ord
ལོ་ case.fin
| punc

case.term

Terminative case. The terminative case is any of the allomorphs རྩུ་ -ru, ལྷ་ -su, རུ་ -tu, རུ་ -du, ར་ -r, when suffixed to a noun, noun phrase or verbal noun. It can have a locative meaning. In addition, it can form adverbs.

(27) ལྷ་འི་གནས་སུ་ “in a deities’ place” (MB D 140r3 - Bialek 2022 p.75)

The terminative can also be used also to express a beneficiary or a result of an action and it

can mark oblique arguments of certain verbs (for more examples see Bialek 2022 p.75).

3.4 Clitics

cl.focus

Focus clitic. Focus clitics ལྱང་ and ཡང་ are tagged cl.focus. Other words currently tagged with this tag include: འང་, ཅང་, and སྤྱིར་ཡང་. The word ལྟ་ when it is not tagged as a verb, or a relator noun, is also tagged as a focus clitic.

cl.top

Topic clitic. This tag is introduced for the topic clitic *-ni* ནི་ . In this way we can automatically create a topic phrase NP-TOP with the automatic chunkparsing.

(28) དེ་བཞིན་གཤམས་པ་ནི་ཡོན་ཏན་མངའོ། “Regarding Tathāgata, [he] possesses excellent qualities.” (MB D 138v6, Bialek 2022 p.119)

cl.quot

Quotative clitic. The 'quotative clitic' has the allomorphs ཅེས་, ཞེས་, and ཤེས་. The forms ཅེ་ན་, ཅེས་ བ, etc. reveal that these are originally verbs, but in order to do justice to their new function and to facilitate research into (in)direct speech, we keep the tag cl.quot. A selection of words tagged with this tag are: ཞེས་, ཅེས་, ཞེས་པ་, ཞེ་, ཅེས་པ་, ཤེ་, ཅེ་, ཅེས་པ་, ཞེས་ (a misspelling of ཞེས་), and ཞེས་བ.

3.5 Converbs

Unlike the name suggests, converbs in this annotation manual are not actually verbs, but the subordinate conjunctions attached to subordinate clause verbs. These 'converbs' are homophonous with their case marking counterparts, but will be tagged "cv.X" instead of "case.X" because they always follow verbs. Note that to be consistent, after verbal nouns, these markers are always tagged "case.X", because of the noun-like nature of the verbal noun.

cv.abl

There are few cases when cv.abl occurs after a verb stem. The ablative converb is the morpheme ལས་ *-las* when it follows a verb. It usually means origin/source:

(29)

འཕགས་པ་ n.v.invar

ཐོགས་མེད་ n.prop

ཐུབ་པ་དཔག་བསམ་གཤམ་ n.count

ལྱུང་ v.past.gyur

ལས་ cv.abl

| punc

cv.agn

Agentive converb. The agentive converb has the allomorphs གིས་ *-gis*, གྱིས་ *-gyis*, ཀྱིས་ *-kyis*, when it follows a verb. It forms causal clauses.

(30)

ང་ p.pers
མི་ neg
ཉན་ v.fut.v.pres
གྱིས་ cv.agn
ཚོད་ p.pers
དང་ case.ass
ཚོ་གྲག་ n.count
དུ་ case.term
བྱ་ v.fut.byed
དགོས་ v.invar.dgos
མོ་ cv.fin
| punc
<utt>

cv.all

Allative converb. The allative converb is the clitic morpheme ལ་ *-la* when it follows a verb. It has a coordinative function between two clauses.

(31) སྐག་མོ་འདི་ནི་ཉམ་ཚུང་ལ་རིད་པ་ “this tigress, that was weak and (ལ་) meagre”
(MB D 139r5, Bialek 2022, p. 148)

cv.are

The converb are (འརེ). This tag is used to tag the converb ཏ་རེ་ and its allomorphs (cf. Walter Wimon, 1967, 'The Tibetan Particle "re",' Bulletin of the School of Oriental and African Studies, 30.1, pp. 117-126). It is worth noting that the Tibetan sentences ending in འརེ་ are often preceded by sentences ending in an imperative; the two kinds of sentences have to be considered (and translated) together.

(32) ཐམས་ཅད་སྐྱབས་བཟུལ་བར་གྱུར་ཏ་རེ་ “lest misfortune should befall us all”
(Vinayavastu ; Ti. T, XLI,237a1= N, hDul, Kha, 559A)

cv.ass

Associative converb. The associative converb is the clitic morpheme དང་ *-dang* if it follows a verb. This tag is particularly used with the polite imperative meaning of དང་. It is added at the end of an imperative clause in order to connect this clause with the following, indicative one. When དང་ connects an imperative clause with another clause, it also signals that the next

clause has a subject distinct from the imperative clause.

- (33) མཆེད་གཉིས་མྱུར་གཤེགས་ཤིག་དང་། བདག་དོན་ཞིག་གཉེར་ཏེ། སྤྲོད་བཞིན་པར་མཆིའོ།
 “Oh, brothers, go on ahead! Having taken care of something, I will come after.”
 (MB D 139v2, Bialek 2022 p.146)

cv.cont

Continuing converb. The continuing converb is formally similar to the genitive followed by -ན and functionally similar to the imperfective converb in earlier strata of literature. The words tagged with this tag are: ཞིན་, གྱིན་, རྒྱིན་. The function of this particle is to connect the main verb with the following special verb. Their common trait is that they express the progressive aspect.

- (34) ཚོས་ཟབ་མོ་སྤོང་པ་ཉིད་ལ་མོས་པར་བེད་གིན་ཡོད་དུས། “While [the monkey] was devoting itself to the profound Buddhist teaching, the voidness, [. . .].”
 (GLR 22r4, Bialek p.195)

cv.ela

Elative converb. The elative converb is the clitic morpheme ཅས་ -nas when it follows verbs. It has a resultative function.

- (35) ལྷ་མོ་དེས་དེ་སྐད་སྒྲུབ་པ་ཐོས་ནས་ཁམས་ཏེ། “When the queen had heard these words uttered, [she] fainted away.”
 (MB D 139v7–140r1, Bialek 2022, p.144)

cv.fin

Sentence-final particle after verbs. The sentence-final particle is an explicit marker of a finite verb in the indicative mood. Words tagged with this tag include: མོ, འོ, དོ, ངོ, མོ, ཏོ, རོ, ལོ, སོ, འོ, བོ, མོ, and མོ.

- (36) དེའི་ཚེ་སྐྱག་མོས་རྒྱལ་བུའ་ཤ་ན་ཟད་པར་ཟོས་སོ། “By that time the tigress has completely eaten the flesh of the prince[’s body].”
 (MB D 140r1. Bialek 2022, p.119)

cv.gen

Genitive converb. The genitive converb is any of the allomorphs ཞི་ -gi, རྒྱི་ -gyi, རྒྱི་ -kyi, འི་ -’i, ཡི་ -yi, when it follows a verb. It usually marks an adversative relationship between the preceding verb and the following one. If the verb is negated then it has more of a concessive meaning, rendered as “although”, “but”.

- (37) སྤིག་པ་བྱས་པ་ན་སེམས་ཅན་དམྱལ་བར་ལྷུང་གི། དགོ་བ་བྱས་ན་མཐོ་ངོས་སུ་སྦྱེད་སྟེ།
 “If [one] committed an offence, [he] will fall to hell. Whereas (ཞི་), if [one] did good deeds, [he] will be reborn in heaven.”
 (MB D 140r7, Bialek 2022, p.147)

cv.impf

Imperfective converb. The imperfective converb is the morpheme that has the three allomorphs ཞིང་, ཅིང་, and ཤིང་ and always follows a verb. This converb can frequently be rendered with “and” in English and it has mainly a coordinate function between two predicates.

(38) ལྷོ་པོ་དེ་ཕྱི་རུ་ལྟོ་ལྟོ་ལྟོ་ཅིང་དོང་དོ། Lit. “The king took a walk outside and went.”
(MB D 139r3–4, Bialek 2022, p.108)

cv.loc

Locative converb. The locative converb is the clitic morpheme ན་ when it follows a verb. It has a conditional function:

(39) ལྷོ་བ་ཡོད་ན་ངེས་པར་འཇིག་གོ། “If [something] has birth, [it] will certainly perish.”
(MB D 140r6–7, Bialek 2022 p.145)

For more examples see Bialek 2022, p.145-146.

cv.ipv

Imperative converb. The imperative converb is the morpheme that explicitly marks the imperative or prohibitive mood, which has one of the three allomorphs ཤིག་, ཅིག་, and ཞིག་. ཤིག་པ་ is also tagged with this tag.

(40) བདག་ལ་སློམ་ཤིག་ “Tell us!” (MB D 140r5, Bialek p.93)

cv.odd

Odd converbs. Odd converbs are any that we discovered after fixing the tagset. So far we the following words with this tag: ལས་ཆེ, ཨང་, ཚད་. We acknowledge that that this not a good tag, but we need to do research on each of the individual markers in this category before we can give them their own tag.

cv.ques

Question converb. The question converb is any allomorph of the marker ལས་, which is an explicit marker of a polar questions or alternate questions. Words tagged with this tag include: ལས་, མས་, ཉས་, དས་, ཀས་, ངས་, ཅས་, ཆས་, ཇས་, ཉས་, བས་, མས་, ཇེ་, and མེ་.

(41) Polar question: ལྷོ་པོ་ཡོད་དམ། “Is there anybody suitable?”
(MB D 139r7, Bialek p.136)

(42) Alternate questions: བདེན་ནམ་མི་བདེན། “Is [it] true or false (lit. not true)?”
(ML D 18v, Bialek p.136)

cv.rung

The converb རུང་. When the morpheme རུང་ appears after a verb it functions as a converb with a concessive meaning.

- (43) ཨ་ཁུ་དང་ཨ་ཞེ་གཉིས་ཅི་ལ་མི་འཆམ་རུང་གློ་ལ་འཆམ་པ་དང་། “Although the paternal uncle and aunt never agreed on anything, [they] did agree on food.”
(ML D 12r, Bialek 2022 p.200)

cv.sem

Semi-final converb. The semi-final converb is the morpheme that has the three allomorphs ཏེ, ཏྟེ, and ཏེ. It usually follows a verb and it is also called gerundial particle - it can introduce a fact, person, event, described in more details in the following sentence (can be rendered as “and” or with a semicolon in English) or - as the name suggests - it can have a gerundial function. In both cases the verb preceding the cv.sem and the verb of the main clause (usually followed by a cv.fin) have the same subject.

- (44) འཇམ་བུ་སྒྲིང་འདི་ན་རྒྱལ་པོ་ཤིང་རྟ་ཆེན་པོ་ཞེས་བྱ་བ་ཞིག་ཡོད་དེ། རྒྱལ་པོ་ལྔ་ལྔ་སྟོང་སྟོང་ལ་དབང་བྱེད་དོ།། “There was a king called Śiñ-rta-čhen-po in this continent; [he] was ruling over about five thousand vassals.”
(MB D 139r2, Bialek 2022, p.118)

- (45) དེ་ནས་བྲག་སྲིན་མོ་ལངས་ཏེ། སྤེལ་ལ་འདྲི་ཅེས་བེད་དོ།།
“The rock demoness arose and asked the monkey thus.” (GLR 22r6, Bialek 2022, p.118)

For more examples and specific uses of the cv.sem see Bialek 2022 pp. 118-119.

cv.term

Terminative converb. The terminative converb is any of the allomorphs རུ་ -ru, ལུ་ -su, ཏུ་ -tu, ཏུ་ -du, ར་ -r, when it follows a verb or a verbal noun. The terminative after the verb stem marks an infinitive clause that expresses purpose of an action:

- (46) བདག་གི་བུ་དགུམ་པ་ལ་བྱུག་པ་འདིའི་སྐབས་མཇུག་ཏུ་གསོལ། “[I] beg [you] to save these sons of mine who are about to be killed.”
(MB D 138v, Bialek 2022 p.146)

3.6 Determiners

Determiners are tagged d.X. We distinguish between demonstratives, emphasising determiners, indefinite markers, plural markers, quantifiers and "tsam".

d.dem

Demonstrative. This tag is used for the demonstratives འདི 'this' and དེ 'that'. These two words are tagged as demonstratives also when used as determiners (i.e. we do not distinguish རྒྱལ་པོ་དེ 'that king' from དེ 'that one, him'). Words tagged with this tag include: དེ, འདི, ཡ, ཚུ, མ, ས, སྤྱ, ས་གི, མ་གྱི, མ་གི, མ་གྱི, འདི་པ, ཡ་གི.

d.emph

Emphasising determiner. This category is for ཉིད་ in phrases such as རྒྱལ་པོ་ཉིད་ 'that very king' or ལུས་ཉིད་ 'this body'. This syntactic use of ཉིད་ must be distinguished from its use in Buddhist terminology -ཉིད་ inside of words, e.g. ལྗང་པ་ཉིད་ 'emptiness'. Apart from ཉིད་, ལོན་ 'the very, same' is also tagged as d.emph. This use of ལོན་ should not be confused with its function as a third person pronoun in Old Tibetan. In one case ལོ་ appears not as a personal pronoun but as what seems to be a variant of ལོན་; this ལོ་ we also classify as an emphatic, e.g.

(47) སྐྱེས་པའི་ཚིག་འདི་བདེན་ན་བདེན་པའི་ཚིག་བདེན་པའི་ཚིག་སྐྱེས་པས། བདག་གི་ལུས་འདི་ལྷ་མ་ལོ་བཞིན་དུ་
སྐྱ་མེད་པར་གྱུར་ཅིག་ 'If these words that I have said are true, then because of saying true words, let this my body be without wounds like before' (D341, vol 74, page 137b).

Words tagged with this tag include: ཉིད་, ལོན་, ལོ་, and ལོ་.

d.indef

Indefinite article. This category is used for the allomorphs of the indefinite marker ཅིག་, ཞིག་, ཤིག་ as in ཤོན་ ཅིག་ 'a messenger'. The indefinite marker, which occurs inside of noun phrases, must be distinguished from the identically looking imperative converb (see [cv.ipv](#)), which occurs suffixed to the imperative stems of verbs.

d.plural

Plural marker. The plural markers རྣམས་, དག་, and ཚོ་ are tagged as their own category 'plural'. However, plural pronouns (བདག་ཅག་, ཞེད་ཅག་, ལུ་བྱ་ཅག་) are treated as one word and tagged as pronouns (see [p.pers](#)). Words tagged with this tag include: རྣམས་, དག་, ཡོངས་, སྐྱེས་པས་, ཚོ་.

d.quant

Quantifier. For quantifiers like གུན་ 'all', ཐམས་ཅད་ 'all', གཞན་ 'other', ཀྱང་ 'all', ག་ 'all' - usually found after numbers, རེ་ and རེ་རེ་ 'each', ཤ་སྟག་ 'only, all', ལ་ 'some', ཡ་རེ་ 'each one of two', སྤུ་རེ་ 'a few', གཞིན་ '?', མང་པོ་ 'many', སྤྱི་ 'all', ཚུང་ཟད་ 'a few', ལུ་མ་ 'many', ཤས་ 'some, a few', མཐའ་དག་ 'all', ཚུང་ཟད་ 'a little', སྐྱ་དགུ་ 'all kinds of' (English quantifiers are 'all, every, some, a few, a lot, many, etc.'). Note many of these markers can also be used as arguments, in which case they are tagged [p.indef](#).

(48)

ཅི་ n.count

ཐམས་ཅད་ d.quant

གོག་པོ་ n.count

ར་ case.term
སོང་ v.past.gro
| punc

(49)

ཁོང་ p.pers
གྲོགས་པོ་ n.count
རྣམས་ d.plural
ནི་ cl.top
ཕུག་རྟེན་ n.count
གཞིན་ d.quant
ཙམ་ d.tsam
ལས་ case.abl
མི་ neg
གཏོང་བ་ n.v.pres
ར་ case.term
འདུག་ v.invar.dug
ང་ p.pers
ས་ case.agn
གསེར་གཡུ་ n.mass
ཀུན་ d.quant
ལུལ་ v.past
ཏེ་ cv.sem
| punc
<utt>

(50)

ད་ adv.temp
ལྟ་ n.rel
ཚེས་པ་ n.count
བཟང་པོ་ adj
ར་ case.term
རྫོམ་པ་ n.v.invar
འི་ case.gen
མི་ n.count
བསོད་ནམས་ཅན་ adj
འགའ་ d.quant
| punc
<utt>

(51)

ལུག་ n.count
སྣ་དགུ་ d.quant
བཏང་ v.past
རྗེས་ n.rel
གསོན་སྣང་ n.count

ལ་ case.all
དམར་ v.invar
འདོན་ v.pres
བྱེད་ v.pres.byed
ཟེར་བ་ n.v.fut.n.v.pres
ལ་ case.all
| punc
<utt>

(52)

དྲིན་ n.count
གཞོན་པ་ n.v.invar
རྒྱུ་ཟད་ d.quant
ཡུང་ cl.focus
མ་ neg
བྱས་པ་ n.v.past

(53)

ངན་སོང་ n.count
གྱི་ case.gen
སྐྱུག་བསྐྱེལ་ n.count
མཐའ་དག་ d.quant
ལས་ case.abl
སྐྱོབ་པ་ n.v.pres
ར་ case.term
མཛད་པ་ n.v.invar.mdzad
ལགས་ v.invar.lags
སོ་ cv.fin
| punc
<utt>

(54)

དེ་ d.dem
ར་ case.term
ཞག་ n.count
ཤས་ d.quant
བཞུགས་པ་ n.v.invar
ས་ case.agn
རྩི་མོ་ n.count
ཞབས་ n.count
ཕྱི་ n.rel
ར་ case.term
འབྲངས་པ་ n.v.past

(55)

གཡོ་ཐབས་ n.count

དུ་མ་ d.quant

ས་ case.agn

ཁང་ n.count

ཞིང་ n.count

ཕྱོགས་ v.past

| punc

<utt>

(56)

གདམས་ངག་ n.count

ལྷི་ d.quant

ལ་ case.all

རང་བུན་ n.count

ཚུད་ v.past.v.pres

ནས་ cv.ela

| punc

<utt>

(57)

ཐུགས་ n.count

བསྐྱེད་བ་ n.v.invar

འི་ case.gen

མི་ n.count

མང་པོ་ d.quant

གྲི་ཁ་ n.count

ར་ case.term

ཤི་བ་ n.v.past

གཟིགས་ v.past.v.pres

ནས་ cv.ela

| punc

<utt>

(58)

ཉུང་པོས་ n.count

གཉིས་ num.card

ཀླ་ d.quant

འི་ case.gen

མངོན་པ་ n.count

(59)

ཡབ་ཡུམ་ n.count

ལྱི་ case.gen

ཐུགས་ n.count

ཀླ་ d.quant

ར་ case.term

བཏང་ v.past

མི་ neg
འཚལ་ v.invar.tshal2
། punc
<utt>

(60)
རྣམ་ཐར་ n.count
ཡང་ cl.focus
དེ་ d.dem
ཀྱ ດ.quant
ས་ case.agn
འཕྲོངས་ v.invar
། punc
<utt>

(61)
ཕྱོད་ adv.temp
ལ་ case.all
ཐོག་ཆེན་ n.count
འདི་ d.dem
རྒྱ་ n.count
བཟང་ v.invar
ལ་ cv.all
འབྲས་བུ་ n.count
ལ་ ດ.quant
གཡེལ་བ་ n.v.fut.n.v.pres
འདྲ་ v.invar.dra2
གསུང་ v.invar

(62)
བརྒྱ་བྱིན་ n.prop
དང་ case.ass
ཚངས་པ་ n.prop
འི་ case.gen
རྒྱལ་པོ་ n.count
ས་ case.agn
ལག་པ་ n.count
ཡ་རེ་ ດ.quant
ནས་ case.ela
ཟེན་ v.invar
ཏེ་ cv.sem
། punc
<utt>

d.tsam

Tsam and words with similar distribution. Words tagged with this tag include ཚས་, ལྷེད་, ཚས་

པ་, རྗེད་ (a misspelling for རྗེད་), ཚམས་, རྗེད་, and རྗེད་པ་.

3.7 Interjections

Interj

Interjection. This tag is used for interjections. Words tagged with this tag include: གྲེ་མ་, གྲེ་, ཨ་ལ་ལ་, གྲི་རུད་, ལོ་དེ་, མ་ལ་, འོ་དོད་, ཉེ་, ཨོ་མ་, and ཨོ་ཨོ་.

3.8 Nouns

n.temp

Temporal noun. Temporal nouns are those that occur in syntactic positions or have morphological structure that suggests they are nouns. They refer to time, and are generally not followed by case markers. Examples of temporal nouns are: ད་, རྗེད་, རྗེད་, ད་དུང་, རང་པ་, རྗེད་ཉིན་, ལ་སང་, དོ་རྒྱུབ་, གཤོད་, ཉིན་, དེ་རིང་, དེང་, རྒྱུབ་, མཚན་མོ་, ཅིག་ཅར་, གཤོད་, རོག་མ་, དབྱར་, དིང་སང་, མདང་, མཚན་, སང་, དགུན་, དེང་སང་, རང་ས་པ་, རྗེད་, ཡུན་རིང་, རོད་, གཤུགས་ཚོད་, གཤུགས་, གུང་, རྗེད་ལྟ་, ཉིན་མཚན་, ད་ལོ་, རང་, རང་ས་, རྗེད་, མཚན་ཡལ་, འདང་, རྗེད་ཚད་, ལར་ཚང་, རྒྱགས་, གཤུང་, གཤོད་མ་, ཉིན་ཞག་ལྷགས་, ད་ཚང་, ད་རུང་, དོ་རྒྱུབ་, རང་པ་, རང་ས་པ་, རྗེད་པ་ཞིག་, རྒྱུབ་མོ་, རྗེད་ལྟ་, མཚན་ཐོག་ཐག་, འཚར་ལ་, འདང་གསུམ་, འཕྲོ་, རྗེད་, སང་ཉིན་, སང་དགོང་, སང་རང་པ་, རྗེད་ལྟ་, རྗེད་ལྟ་, རྗེད་ལྟ་, རྗེད་ལྟ་.

n.count

Count noun. Lexical nouns head a noun phrase and can have nominal suffixes such as -མོ་, -མོ་ and -བ་. We treat a -མ་ or -བ་ as part of the preceding word, regardless of the part-of-speech of the preceding word. Sanskrit terms, e.g. ལྷན་རྒྱ་ལྷན་ 'parivrājaka', are treated as a noun together because it looks like a verb phrase, but functions syntactically as a noun.

In general, when two nouns occur in succession they are understood as a compound; the dvandva compound ས་མ་ 'parents' is treated as one noun rather than two (ས་ 'father' and མ་ 'mother') and the tatpuruṣa compound རྒྱུ་བདག་ 'householder' is likewise treated as one noun rather than two (རྒྱུ་ 'home' and བདག་ 'lord'). When an adjective precedes its head this is also treated as a compound. Thus, because དུག་བཙན་མོ་ would be the expected order for 'mighty poison', we treat བཙན་དུག་ 'mighty poison' (vol. 74, page 147a) as a single word.

Apposition is the one category of exceptions when the concatenation of two nouns is not treated as a compound. An example of this type is the two words ལྷན་ལྷན་ in the following sentence:

(63) དེའི་ཆེ་ཡུལ་དེ་ན་རྒྱུ་བདག་ཅིག་ལ་ལྷན་ལྷན་ཞིག་བཙན་ལྷན་། 'At that time, in that land, when a child, a son, was born to a householder'.

Rather than understanding ལྷན་ as an adjective modifying ལྷན་, or taking ལྷན་ལྷན་ as one word, the second word simply sits after the first one to add greater specificity. The reason to not treat apposition as compounding is because apposition occurs with proper nouns. For example, in the sentence:

(64) དེའི་ཚེ་ན་རྒྱལ་པོ་གསལ་རྒྱལ་གྱི་བཅུ་མོ་ཚེ་པོ་ཉ་བར་ཡི་ཞེས་བྱ་བ་ལ་བྱམོ་ཞིག་བཙས་ནས་ 'At that time a daughter was born to Hbar-li, the main queen of king Prasenajit',

In (64), རྒྱལ་པོ་ 'king' and གསལ་རྒྱལ་ 'Prasenajit' are in apposition; to unite the two as a compound would lead to unintuitive, unwieldy, and therefore have unacceptable consequences.

n.mass

Mass noun. We separate mass nouns from count nouns on the basis of two instances in our corpus where otherwise two nouns not in apposition would follow each other: རྣོ་བྱ་སྤྱོད་གང་ 'a handful of jewels' and རྒྱ་སྤྱོད་པ་གང་ 'a handful of water'. Knowing that there exists this syntactic difference between count nouns and mass nouns, we tag all plausible mass nouns on the basis of their meaning (e.g. ཟངས་ 'copper'). A final list of mass nouns can only be securely put forward after the syntactic behavior of these words is better investigated. Words tagged with this tag include: གསེར་, རྒྱ་, རིན་པོ་ཆེ་, རྣོ་, ཤ་, རྒྱ་, ས་, ལྷག་, ཆང་, སྤྲོད་, སེར་བ་, རྣོ་བྱ་, མར་, རྒྱ་སྤྱོད་, དུལ་, ཡི་གེ་, རས་, ལྷགས་, སྤྱོད་, གངས་, ཚན་དན་, གསེར་གཡུ་, གོས་, དར་, ཤེལ་, གསེར་དུལ་, བཟང་རྒྱ་ག་, མར་ལུ་, ཟངས་, གོས་དར་, རྒྱ་སྤྱོད་, བཟའ་ལྷག་, བཟའ་, བསྐྱེ་ཆང་, བྱམ་རྒྱ་, བྱི་རྒྱུ་, མཐོ་ལྷང་, རིན་ཆེན་, སྤྲོད་བྱ་, ལ་བ་, རྒྱ་སྤྱོད་, ཉ་བྱིས་, ཐལ་བ་, ཐུད་, དབྱས་ལྷག་, ལུར་, མཐོ་མཐིང་, མར་གད་, མར་སར་, ཚོས་, བམ་བཅུད་, འཇིས་པ་, འདག་, རིན་ཆེན་གསེར་, རྒྱགས་རྒྱ་, རྒྱལ་ཚོན་, རྒྱག་ལྷག་, ལ་ཅ་, ལ་ཆ་, ལེ་བཟན་, ཤ་ལྷག་, སེང་ལྷང་, སེང་ལྷང་, སེར་, སྤེ་, སྤེན་བད་.

n.prop

Proper nouns. This tag is used for proper nouns, i.e. personal and place names.

(65)

བཙོམ་ལྷན་འདས་ n.count

ཤུ་སེང་གི་ n.prop

ལ་ case.all

ཕྱག་ n.count

འཚལ་ v.fut.v.pres.tshal1

ལོ་ cv.fin

(66)

ལག་ལྷན་ n.count

མོད་ n.prop

གྱི་ case.gen

མཁས་མཚོག་ n.count

རྣམས་ d.plural

ལ་ case.all

འདུད་ v.fut.v.pres

| punc

n.rel

Relator nouns. A relator noun is a noun, normally one syllable, which has a genitive before it and a spatial case (allative, locative, terminative) after it, e.g. དེའི་ནང་ན་ 'inside of that', དེའི་དྲུང་དུ་ 'before him', དེའི་ལོག་ཏུ་ 'under that', དེའི་ཚེ་ན་ 'at that time'; relator nouns are not quantified and do

not have adjectives, determiners or demonstratives. After identifying the class of relator nouns, these words are tagged as relator nouns even in syntactic contexts missing the genitive to left or the spatial case to the right.

For example, in the sentence:

(67) དེའི་ཚོ་སློབ་པོ་ཞིག་གི་སྤྱི་ལོ་ནས་ནང་དུ་འོངས་པ་ལས། མི་བཙོན་དུ་བཟུང་བ་མཐོང་བ་དང། 'Then the minister went inside from outside and saw the man who had been taken to prison'

In (67), the relator noun ཚོ་ is not followed by a spatial case and the relator noun ནང་ is not preceded by a genitive. In the phrase བར་འགའ་ 'sometimes' we do not consider བར་ a relator noun because it undergoes quantification, e.g.

(68) ... བར་འགའ་ཀི་གཏི་མུག་གི་སྤྱིར་ལུས་བཏང་ཡང་ཚོས་ཀྱི་སྤྱིར་བསོད་ནམས་ཀྱི་ཞིང་དང་ལན་འགའ་ཡང་མ་སྤང་བའི་ལུས་འདི་ཅི་རུད། 'What is the use of this body which ... sometimes has been used because of ignorance, but has not yet met an occasion (to serve) as a field of merit'.

Words tagged with this tag include: ལྟ་, ཕྱི་, བཞིན་, ཚོ་, སྐད་, བར་, དུས་, ནང་, རྗེས་, ལྟར་, ལྟ་བུ་, འདྲ་, འོག་, ལྟེང་, ལྟ་བུ་, སྤྱད་, ངང་, ཕྱོགས་, མཐའ་, མོ་, བཞིན་, ས་, སྤྱོད་, མཐུན་, དབུས་, ཐོག་, ཁོང་, ཕྱི་བཞིན་, ལ་, ཚེད་, ཐོག་མ་, སྐབས་, ལོང་, རྟིང་, ཐང་, གན་, མཇུག་, འཕྲལ་, འོགས་, ཁོང་, རྟེན་, སྤྱད་, ཁོངས་, གསེབ་, ཐམ་, དུས་, ལུ་, ལྟར་, བསེབ་, མགོ་, ཅ་, རིང་, ཚུ་, ལྟག་, སྟོར་, དཀྱིལ་, དབུང་, བྱང་, མཐའ་, འོགས་, ལྟན་, ཞོར་, འཕྲིས་, འོག་བ་, ལྱབ་, སྟེ་, སྟེད་, སྟེང་ལ་, སྟེངས་, སྟོད་. Several questions of delimiting relator nouns require further consideration, in particular, the approach to ལྟ་ versus ལྟ་བུ་.

n.son

Noun 'son'. We use this tag for སྲས་ In this way we can automatically create NP-NPR for things like 'Ngawang's son'.

3.9 Verbal Nouns

Verbs are nominalised by adding a nominaliser like བ་, བ་, ལྟལ་, མཁན་, མི་, or ས་ to the respective stems, in which case they get a verbal noun tag n.v.X. Note that in general, verbs derived from adjectives are (n.)v.invar unless they have -s, in which case they are (n.)v.past. Verbal nouns can appear in all different tenses/moods we distinguish for verbs in general. Just like with verbs, the tense/aspect/mood indication is based on morphology only (see section on [verbs](#)). We do not derive potential tense or mood labels from the syntactic context as this would entail adding linguistic analysis into the annotation, which we avoid (see general principles in the introduction above).

n.v.fut

Nominalization of a future verb stem. This tag is used for the nominalized versions of future verb stems, i.e. a future verb stem followed by བ་, བ་, ལྟལ་, མཁན་, མི་, or ས་. Some examples are given in (68) and (69) below.

(69)

རབ་ adv.intense
དུ་ cv.term
དབྱེ་བ་ n.v.fut
ཉིད་ d.emph
ཀྱིས་ case.agn
དང་ case.ass
| punc

(70)

ཀྱིས་པ་ n.count
འདི་ d.dem
རྣམས་ d.plural
ཀྱིས་ case.agn
ཞེད་ p.pers
ཀྱི་ case.gen
འབབ་ས་ n.v.fut
དང་ case.ass

n.v.fut.n.v.past

Nominalization of a future or past stem of a verb. This tag is used for verb stems with the same form in the future and in the past, followed by nominalisers like བ་, བ་, ཚུལ་, མཁན་, མི་, or ས་.

(71)

ཆེད་ n.rel
དུ་ case.term
བརྗོད་པ་ n.v.fut.n.v.past
འི་ case.gen
མཇུ་ n.count
ཉེ་ cl.focus
| punc

n.v.fut.n.v.pres

Nominalization of a future or present stem of a verb. This tag is used for verb stems with the same form in the future and in the present, followed by nominalisers like བ་, བ་, ཚུལ་, མཁན་, མ, or ས་.

(72)

རྗོད་པ་ n.count
གསུམ་ num.card
དུ་ case.term
འཇོག་པ་ n.v.fut.n.v.pres
འི་ case.gen
རྒྱ་མཚན་ n.count
དང་ case.ass
| punc

n.v.ipv

Nominalization of an imperative stem of a verb. The imperative stem of a verb is usually not supposed to be nominalized. However, in rare cases there are nominalised forms which appear to come from imperative stems, and we mark them accordingly.

(73)

ལྟ་ལ་ n.count
ལྟོང་པོ་ n.count
ས་ case.agn
ལྟུབས་པ་ n.v.ipv
ཡིན་ v.fut.v.pres.yin
| punc

n.v.invar

Nominalization of invariant verbs. This tag is used for invariant verb stems. Invariant verb stems are so called because they have the same form in the present, future and past. When they are nominalised, they are followed by nominalisers like བ་, བ་, ལྟུལ་, མཁལ་, མི་, or ས་.

(74)

ལྟ་བཤོས་ n.count
ལྟུ་ case.gen
ལྟུལ་ས་ n.v.invar
ལྟོང་ས་ n.v.invar
ཡིན་ v.fut.v.pres.yin
| punc

n.v.past

Nominalization of a past verb stem. This tag is used for the nominalized versions of past verb stems, i.e. a past verb stem followed by nominalisers like བ་, བ་, ལྟུལ་, མཁལ་, མི་, or ས་.

(75)

མང་པ་ n.prop
ས་ case.agn
ལྟ་ n.count
ལྟོང་ v.past
ནས་ cv.ela
ལྟོང་ས་ n.v.past
ས་ case.agn
| punc

n.v.past.n.v.pres

Nominalization of a past or present stem of a verb. This tag is used for verb stems with the same form in the past and in the present, followed by nominalisers like བ་, བ་, ལྟུལ་, མཁལ་, མི་, or ས་.

(76)

འདི་ d.dem

འདྲ་ n.rel

འི་ case.gen

མིང་རྒྱུང་ n.count

ལས་ n.count

ཀྱིས་ case.agn

ཟིན་པ་ n.v.past.n.v.pres

རྣམས་ d.plural

| punc

n.v.pres

Nominalization of a present verb stem. This tag is used for the nominalized versions of present verb stems, i.e. a present verb stem followed by nominalisers like པ་, བ་, རྒྱལ་, མཁན་, མི་, or ས་.

(77)

པ་ས་ n.count

ཡང་ cl.focus

སྐབས་ n.v.pres

ས་ case.agn

འདྲོངས་ v.past

| punc

3.10 Negation

Negation in Tibetan can be marked by a negative marker or by a negative verb. For the two verbs མིན་ and མེད་ negation is inherent to their meaning, but these verbs are therefore added to the list of [special verbs](#). In this section, we only discuss negative markers.

neg

Negation. The two negation prefixes མ་ *ma* and མི་ *mi* are classified together in their own category. The polar question prefix ཞེ་ *e* is also categorised under this tag because it occupies the same syntactic position as མ་ and མི་.

3.11 Numerals

In numbers we distinguish cardinals (གཅིག་ གཉིས་ གསུམ་ etc.) and ordinals (དང་པོ་ གཉིས་པ་ གསུམ་པ་ etc.).

numeral

Actual numbers, e.g. "1967" or Tibetan ལ་ are tagged as numeral.

(78)

1967 numeral

ལོ་ n.count

ར་	case.ter
སྐྱེ་དམན་	n.count
འདི་	d.dem
ཚོས་	n.mass
འཛིན་ཆས་	n.count
མང་པོ་	adj
ཉོས་	v.past

| punc

(Goldstein 1993, p.90)

num.card

Cardinal number. Cardinal numbers are tagged num.card. In higher numbers each component digit is tagged separately to provide more insight into the internal structure. When a numeral follows a noun we regard the two as separate words. In addition to obvious cases like མི་ལྔ་ 'five men', we also treat དགོན་མཚོག་གསུམ་ 'triratna' as two words. We treat སྤྲུལ་ as a cardinal number. There are occasions when the morphology of a word suggests that it might contain a numeral (e.g. མངོན་སུམ་ 'real', ཡུན་སུམ་ཚོགས་ 'marvellous'), but there is no reason to see such cases as synchronically analysable. Numbers that end with -པོ་ are also tagged num.card. Derivatives of numerals are treated according to the function they have in the sentence, thus གཅིག་པ་ 'sole' is an adjective, གཉིག་ 'both' is an indefinite pronoun, etc.

num.ord

Ordinal number. Ordinal numbers are tagged num.ord. Some adjectives can be distinguished from ordinal numbers only in context. For example, in the phrase རྡོ་རྗེ་རྩ་ལྔ་པ་ 'a five-pronged vajra' the noun phrase syntax and the overall meaning of the passage dictates that ལྔ་པ་ is part of the word རྩ་ལྔ་པ་ 'five-pronged' rather than an ordinal number 'fifth'.

3.12 Pronouns

Pronouns can be used to refer to real-life entities or those that are mentioned in the contexts. We distinguish between indefinite, interrogative, personal and reflexive pronouns.

p.indef

Indefinite pronoun. The words ལ་ལ་ 'some', མོ་མོ་ 'each', and གཉིག་ 'both' can function as independent arguments of a sentence ("I like **both**", "**Some** say that's good"), in which case they are not tagged as d.quant, but as indefinite pronouns with the tag 'p.indef'. Other words tagged with this tag include: ལ་, མོ་མོ་, ལ་ལ་, རེ་རེ་, རེ་.

p.interrog

Interrogative pronouns. This is the tag used for interrogative pronouns such as ལྟུ་ 'who', ལྟོ་ 'when', and གང་ 'where'. Words tagged with this tag include: ཅི་, གང་, ཇི་, ཅི་, ལྟུ་, ལྟོ་, ལྟོ་, ཇི་ལྟུ་, གང་, གང་ལྟོ་, ཇི་ཚམས་, ཅི་སྐྱིད་, and ལྟོག་.

p.pers

Personal pronouns. This tag is used for personal pronouns. Words tagged with this tag include: བདག་, རྒྱུད་, ང་, རྒྱུད་, བདག་ཅག་, ངེད་, ཁོ་, ཁོང་, རང་ཅེ་, ཁོ་ལོ་, རང་, མོ་, ཁོ་མོ་, རྒྱུད་ཅག་, འོ་སྐོལ་, ལུ་ཅག་, འོ་ཅག་. The word རང་ is only tagged as p.pers when it functions as a full independent pronoun in its own right; in ང་རང་ and རྒྱུད་རང་ the word རང་ is tagged p.pers. The word བདག་ is tagged as p.pers when it is a humble equivalent of ང་. When this word means 'lord' or 'the self' (philosophy) it is tagged n.count and when it means 'himself' it is tagged as p.refl.

p.refl

Reflexive pronouns. This tag is used for reflexive pronouns. The only word tagged with this tag རང་ and བདག་. The word རང་ is tagged as p.refl when it functions as a reflexive, in a sentence (invented) such as ཁོས་ དེ་རིང་ རང་ གི་ ཟན་ ཟོས་ མོ་ 'Today, he ate his own food' or in long form personal pronouns such as ང་རང་ and རྒྱུད་རང་. When རང་ is full independent pronoun meaning 'I' or 'you' it is tagged p.pers. The word བདག་ is tagged p.refl only when it means 'himself'.

3.13 Punctuations

punc

Punctuation. While a *tsheg*, 'dot' (ཚེག་), is considered part of the preceding syllable, all other punctuation marks are tagged as punctuation. Such marks include །, ་, །།, །།།, and །།།།. Punctuation marks are broken apart to aid tokenization, e.g. we tag །/punc ་/punc །།/punc །།།/punc.

skt

Sanskrit or other metalinguistic elements. This tag was invented for the odd Sanskrit word that occurs in Tibetan (e.g. in mantras) not as a syntactic word in its own right, but as something metalinguistic at least vis à vis Tibetan.

3.14 Verbs

The tense/mood/aspect on the verb is based on the morphology only at this POS-tagging level. Verbs derived from adjectives are (n.)v.invar unless they have -s, in which case they are (n.)v.past. Even adjectives that only have present and past forms would be invar if they are used as verbs and the form is the same, e.g. དཀའ་ 'difficult, hard' (or དཀའ་ before cv.fin) (no future or imperative form for this):

(79)

རབ་ adv.intense

དུ་ cv.term

འབྱུང་བ་ n.v.fut.n.v.pres

ར་ case.term

དཀའ་ v.invar

འོ་ cv.fin

། punc

v.fut

Future stem of a verb. This tag is used for future verb stems.

(80)

ལྷ་མ་ n.count

མྱུ་ adv.temp

ས་ case.agn

བསྐྱུང་ v.fut

ལ་ cv.all

v.fut.v.past

Future or past stem of a verb. This tag is used for verb stems that are morphologically ambiguous between the past and future.

(81)

བསྐྱུང་ v.fut.v.past

ན་ cv.loc

འགྲོ་ v.fut.v.pres.gro

ལྷིང་ n.count

འདོད་ v.invar.dod

v.fut.v.pres

Future or present stem of a verb. This tag is used for verb stems that are morphologically ambiguous between the past and present.

(82)

ཕྱིན་ v.past.gro

ན་ cv.loc

མྱོད་ v.fut.v.pres

ལྷིང་ n.count

འདོད་ v.invar.dod

| punc

v.ipv

Imperative stem of a verb. This tag is used for imperative verb stems.

(83)

རྣམ་འགྲོལ་མ་ n.count

དེ་ d.dem

ནང་ n.count

དུ་ case.term

ཤོས་ v.ipv

ཤོག་ v.invar.shog

གསུང་ v.invar

| punc

v.invar

Present, past, or future stem of a verb. This tag is used for verb stems that are morphologically ambiguous among present, past, and future.

(84)

ལྡོག་ n.count
ནག་པོ་ adj
ལྡོག་ v.invar
ཞིང་ cv.impf
| punc

If a verb has only one stem then we tag the verb as v.invar:

(85)

ལྡོག་མི་ n.count
རྣམས་ d.plural
ལྱི་ case.agn
ལྡོག་པ་ v.fut.v.pres
ལྡོག་ cv.sem
མ་ neg
བརྗོད་ v.invar
ཅིག་ cv.ipv
| punc

If a verb has only two stems and they are morphologically ambiguous, then we tag the verb as v.invar, e.g. Present/Past: དགོ་

(86)

བདག་ p.pers
ཉིད་ d.emph
གཅིག་ལུ་ adj
འི་ case.gen
འཚོ་བ་ n.v.invar
དགོ་ v.invar
| punc

v.past

Past stem of a verb. This tag is used for past verb stems.

(87)

ཞིང་ n.count
འོ་མ་གྱི་གསུང་ n.prop
ཡང་ cl.focus
ཨ་ལུ་ n.count

འི་ case.gen
ལག་ n.count
ནས་ case.ela
བྱངས་ v.past
ཏི་ cv.sem

v.past.v.pres

Past or present stem of a verb. A verb stem that is both morphologically ambiguous between the past and present.

(88)

ནམ་མཁའ་ n.count
ལ་ case.all
འཇམ་ n.count
འི་ case.gen
གུར་ n.count
ཐུབ་ v.past.v.pres
| punc

v.pres

Present stem of a verb. This tag is used for present verb stems.

(89)

ཕུག་མཚོད་ n.count
ལྟ་ n.count
དང་ case.ass
མཁའ་འགྲོ་ n.count
ས་ case.agn
འབྲུག་ v.pres
| punc

3.14.1 Particular Cases

Sometimes a stem can be linked to two different verbs: as བསྐྱོམ་ - which can be present of བསྐྱོམ་ but also future of a different verb སྐྱོམ་ - very similar meanings and both voluntary. We tag this case as **v.fut.v.pres**.

3.14.2 Special verbs

Special Verbs and Verbal Nouns

Although this annotation scheme does not provide full lemmatisation, we do have special tags for a large number of 'special verbs'. These are any verbs that are of special interest from a linguistic point of view, e.g. because they can function as auxiliaries or light verbs, because they change/grammaticalise in later stages of the language, or because they have additional functions, e.g. negation or copula. To make the annotation process more feasible,

we focus only on those verbs that occur relatively frequently (this is checked in our corpora). In the list of 'special verbs' below, the numbers in parenthesis refer to that.

In our special verb tags we don't use ' for the *a-chung* འ for practical reasons: the apostrophe would be confusing as part of a POS tag.

As already explained in section 1 we base our tense-aspect-mood distinctions on morphological form only, i.e. if there is a morphological element that indicates that a verb is past, future or present tense, we tag it as such. We do use an v.ipv tag if the imperative is morphologically distinct from the other forms:

(90) "to do, to make"

བྱེད་ → v.pres.byed

བྱས་ → v.past.byed

བྱ → v.fut.byed

བྱོས་ → v.ipv.byed - alternative form བྱོ

However, often the imperative cannot be morphologically distinguished from other verb forms. In such cases, we consistently provide the tense/aspect/mood tag that is usually associated with that form, e.g. རྒྱན་ 'to be proper, to be the right time' is consistently tagged as v.past.ran as that is what the morphology indicates and the POS tags are based on that. If that same form can also have an imperative function, we add "(ipv)" in parentheses behind the form, to remind annotators that in some contexts, this can have an imperative meaning. If this is the case the POS tag remains based on the original morphology, i.e. v.past.ran, but the imperative will be clear from the context (and this will be made extra clear by the syntactic annotation in the parsed version of the corpus), as shown in (90):

(91) "to taste, to experience"

ལྟོང་ → v.pres.myong1

ལྟངས་ → v.past.myong1 (ipv)

ལྟང → v.fut.myong1

Homophonous special verbs, i.e. those that have different argument structures, get separate tags, e.g. verb1 vs verb2. This facilitates future research on these forms. When doing such research, it is advisable to extract both verbs from the corpus and do a manual check as there may be missing arguments in the sentences. In the following list, the verbs **highlighted in orange** might need an additional manual check in terms of POS tagging, because their argument structure may be more complex. When forms are ambiguous, the list furthermore indicates when these forms are given the special verb tag and/or what the alternative tag is and when that would be used.

གནད་ (72) → v.invar.gda "to be, to be there"

གནད་པ་ → n.v.invar.gda "to be, to be there"

བཟྱིད་ (27) → v.pres.bgyid "to do, to make"

བཟྱིས་ → v.past.bgyid

བྱི → v.ipv.bgyid - alternative form བྱིས་

བཟྱི → v.fut.bgyid
 བཟྱིད་པ་ → n.v.pres.bgyid “to do, to make”
 བཟྱི་བ་ → n.v.fut.bgyid
 བཟྱིས་པ་ → n.v.past.bgyid
 འཇུར་ (191) → v.fut.v.pres.gyur (ipv) “to change, to transform”
 འཇུརད་ → v.pres.gyur - alternative form ལྷུར་ (ipv)
 ལྷུར་ → v.past.gyur - alternative forms ལྷུརད་ (ipv), བལྷུརད་
 བལྷུར་ → v.fut.v.past.gyur
 ལྷུརད་ → v.ipv.gyur
 འཇུར་ “to become”, is resultative of ལྷུར་ “to change, to transform” - note that this is also one of the imperative forms of འཇུགས་/v.invar (this is not a special verb)
 བལྷུར་བ་ → n.v.fut.n.v.past.gyur
 ལྷུར་བ་ → n.v.past.gyur - alternative forms ལྷུརད་བ་ (ipv), བལྷུརད་བ་
 འཇུར་བ་ → n.v.fut.n.v.pres.gyur (ipv)
 འཇུརད་བ་ → n.v.pres.gyur - alternative form ལྷུར་བ་ (ipv)
 ལྷུརད་ → n.v.ipv.gyur
 གྲགས་ (4) → v.invar.grags - “to be known as”
 ཚོག་ (2) → v.invar.chog - “to be suitable, to be able, to be permitted, to be allowed”
 ཚོག་པ་ → n.v.invar.chog - “to be suitable, to be able, to be permitted, to be allowed”
 ཐག་ (114) → v.invar.thag - if preceded by verb + མ་/neg: “as soon as” (otherwise it is a noun “distance”, “cloth”)
 ཐག་པ་ (5) → n.v.invar.thag - if preceded by verb + མ་/neg: “as soon as”
 ཐང་ (4) → v.invar.thang “to be able”
 ཐང་པ་ → n.v.invar.thang “to be able”
 བདུབ་ → v.invar.thub1 “to be able, to make able” - argument structure [Abs. Obl.]
 ཐུབ་ → v.pres.thub1 - argument structure [Abs. Obl.]
 བདུབས་ → v.past.thub1 - argument structure [Abs. Obl.]
 བདུབ་པ་ → n.v.invar.thub1 “to be able, to make able” - argument structure [Abs. Obl.]
 ཐུབ་པ་ → n.v.pres.thub1 - argument structure [Abs. Obl.]
 བདུབས་པ་ → n.v.past.thub1 - argument structure [Abs. Obl.]
 ཐུབ་ → v.invar.thub2 “to be able, capable of” - argument structure [Erg. Abs.] note that this form can be also the present of thub1: even if the ergative is left out, look at oblique preceding ཐུབ་, if there is an oblique immediately preceding the verb then is most likely thub1. Any possible locative case will be at the beginning of the sentence.
 ཐུབ་པ་ → n.v.invar.thub2 “to be able, capable of” - argument structure [Erg. Abs.]. See note above for disambiguating ཐུབ་.
 དཀའ་ → v.invar.dka “to be difficult”
 དཀའ་བ་ (4) → n.v.invar.dka “to be difficult”
 དགོས་ (148) → v.invar.dgos - “to need” note that དགོས་ may perhaps be related as the future stem of འཇོལ་ (Zeisler 2004: 454 n. 138)
 དགོས་ (95) → v.invar.dgos “to need”
 དགོས་པ་ (79) → n.v.invar.dgos - alternative form དགོས་པ་ “to need”
 དྲ་ → v.fut.dra1 - argument structure is [Erg. Abs.]
 དྲས་ → v.past.dra1 - argument structure is [Erg. Abs.]
 དྲོས་ → v.ipv.dra1 - argument structure is [Erg. Abs.]
 དྲ་བ་ → n.v.fut.dra1 - argument structure is [Erg. Abs.]

དྲམ་པ་ → n.v.past.dra1 - argument structure is [Erg. Abs.]
 དྲོམ་པ་ → n.v.ipv.dra1 - argument structure is [Erg. Abs.]
 འདྲ་ → v.pres.dra1 “to cut, to clip” - argument structure is [Erg. Abs.]
 འདྲ་བ་ → n.v.invar.dra1 “to cut, to clip” [Erg. Abs.]
 འདྲ་ (12) → v.invar.dra2 “to be similar” - argument structure [Abs. Ass.]
 འདྲ་བ་ → n.v.invar.dra2 - if preceded by a n.v.*; argument structure is [Abs. Ass.]
 དྲག་ (3) → v.invar.drag “to recover from illness”
 དྲགས་ → v.past.drag
 དྲགས་པ་ → n.v.invar.drag “to recover from illness”
 དྲགས་པ་ → n.v.past.drag
 ལུས་ (97) → v.invar.nus - when preceded by verb or verbal noun + མ་/neg: “to be able” - in other cases, it is the past (or ipv) of ལུ་ and treated as all other verbs
 ལུས་པ་ (53) → n.v.nus.invar - alternative form ལུས་པ་; - when preceded by verb or verbal noun + མ་/neg: “to be able” - in other cases, this form is the past (or ipv) of ལུ་ and treated as all other 'non-special' verbs
 རོད་ → v.past.phod “to handle, to cope with” (ipv)
 རོད་པ་ → n.v.past.phod “to handle, to cope with” (ipv)
 འཕྲོད་ (14) → v.fut.v.pres.phod “to handle, to cope with”
 འཕྲོད་པ་ (11) → n.v.fut.n.v.pres.phod “to handle, to cope with”
 བཙམ་ → v.fut.v.past.tshal1 - the argument structure for tshal1 is [Erg. Abs.]
 བཙམ་དྲ་ → v.past.tshal1 - the argument structure for tshal1 is [Erg. Abs.]
 འཚམ་/v.fut.v.pres.tshal1 རྟོ/ cv.fin: འཚམ་ (9) → v.fut.v.pres.tshal1 - “to greet, to prostrate for respect; (when prefixed by རྟོ) to pay respect” - because of the lack of sandhi in the final particle; the argument structure for tshal1 is [Erg. Abs.]
 འཚམ་/v.past.tshal1 རྟོ/ cv.fin: འཚམ་ → v.past.tshal1 - because of the sandhi in the final particle starting with d-; the argument structure for tshal1 is [Erg. Abs.]
 འཚམ་པ་ → n.v.fut.n.v.pres.tshal1 “to greet, to prostrate for respect; (when prefixed by རྟོ) to pay respect” - the argument structure for tshal1 is [Erg. Abs.]
 བཙམ་པ་ → n.v.fut.n.v.past.tshal1 - the argument structure for tshal1 is [Erg. Abs.]
 བཙམ་དྲ་པ་ → n.v.past.tshal1 - the argument structure for tshal1 is [Erg. Abs.]
 འཚམ་དྲ་པ་ → n.v.past.tshal1 - the argument structure for tshal1 is [Erg. Abs.]
 འཚམ་ → v.invar.tshal2 “to beg, to desire, to ask” - the argument structure for tshal2 is [Abs. Obl.]
 འཚམ་པ་ → n.v.invar.tshal2 “to beg, to desire, to ask” - the argument structure for tshal2 is [Abs. Obl.]
 བཞག་ → v.past.bzhag “to assign, to establish, to designate”
 བཞག་པ་ → n.v.past.bzhag “to assign, to establish, to designate”
 བྱེད་ (105) → v.pres.byed “to do”
 བྱ་ → v.fut.byed
 བྱས་ → v.past.byed
 བྱོས་ → v.ipv.byed - alternative form བྱོས་
 བྱེད་པ་ → n.v.fut.byed
 བྱས་པ་ → n.v.past.byed
 བྱོས་པ་ → n.v.ipv.byed - alternative form བྱོས་པ་
 འབྱུང་ (168) → v.fut.v.pres.byung (ipv) “to arise, to emerge, to appear”
 འབྱུང་པ་ → n.v.fut.n.v.pres.byung (ipv) “to arise, to emerge, to appear”

ལྷུང་ → v.past.byung (ipv)
 ལྷུང་བ་ → n.v.past.byung (ipv)
 མཆི་ (4) → v.fut.v.pres.mchi “to go”
 མཆིས་ → v.past.mchi → the argument structure for mchi is [Obl. Abs.]
 མཆི་བ་ → n.v.fut.n.v.pres.mchi “to go” → the argument structure for mchi is [Obl. Abs.]
 མཆིས་པ་ → n.v.past.mchi → the argument structure for mchi is [Obl. Abs.]
 མཆིས་ → v.invar.mchis “to be, to exist” → the argument structure for mchis [Abs. Obl.]
 མཆིས་པ་ → n.v.invar.mchis “to be, to exist” → the argument structure for mchis [Abs. Obl.]
 མཇེད་ (32) → v.invar.mdzad “to do” (honorific)
 མཇེད་པ་ → n.v.invar.mdzad
 མཇོན་པ་ → n.v.ipv.mdzad
 མིན་/v.fut.v.pres.min མོ་/cv.fin: མིན་ (12) → v.fut.v.pres.min - because of the lack of sandhi in the final particle
 མིན་ → v.past.min
 མིན་/v.past.min རོ་/cv.fin: མིན་ → v.past.min - because of the sandhi in the final particle starting with d-
 མིན་པ་ → n.v.fut.n.v.pres.min
 མིན་པ་ → n.v.past.min
 མེད་ (19) → v.invar.med “to not be, exist” - note that some dictionaries will give two different argument structures, but since they contain the same cases just in a different order this is more likely to be due to focus in copular and existential clauses than that there are really two homophonous verbs med.
 མེད་པ་ → n.v.invar.med “to not be, exist, to be without”
 མོད་ (120) → v.invar.mod - when preceded by a verb: “indeed, although, but, though”
 མོད་པ་ → n.v.invar.mod - when preceded by a verb: “indeed, although, but, though”
 མྱོང་ (6) → v.pres.myong1 “to taste, to perceive” - this form is always transitive with [Erg. Abs.] arguments
 མྱང་ → v.fut.myong1
 མྱངས་ → v.past.myong1 (ipv)
 མྱོང་བ་ → n.v.pres.myong1 “to taste, to perceive” - this form is always transitive with [Erg. Abs.] arguments
 མྱང་བ་ → n.v.fut.myong1
 མྱངས་པ་ → n.v.past.myong1
 མྱོང་ → v.invar.myong2 “to sense, to feel” - v.invar.myong2 is always intransitive
 མྱོང་བ་ → n.v.invar.myong2 “to sense, to feel” - n.v.invar.myong2 is always intransitive
 འགོ་ (39) → v.fut.v.pres.gro “to go”
 འོང་ → v.past.gro - alternative forms ཕྱིན་, ཕྱིན་པ་
 འགོ་བ་ → n.v.fut.n.v.pres.gro “to go”
 འོང་བ་ → n.v.past.gro - alternative forms ཕྱིན་པ་, ཕྱིན་པ་
 འདུག་ (304) → v.invar.dug “is, there is, to exist”
 འདུག་པ་ → n.v.invar.dug “is, there is, to exist”
 འདོད་ (49) → v.invar.dod “to wish, to want”
 འདོད་པ་ → n.v.invar.dod “to wish, to want”
 འོང་ (17) → v.fut.v.pres.ong “to come”
 འོང་བ་ → n.v.invar.ong “to come”
 འོངས་ → v.ong.past (ipv)

འོངས་པ་ → n.v.past.ong

ཤོག་/v.ipv.ong ཅིག་/cv.ipv: note that ཤོག་ is generally regarded as the imperative of འོང་ “to come”, but historically the imperative of གཤེགས་ “to go away, to leave”; when shog is not followed by cv.ipv it can be v.invar.shog or v.ipv.ong. This needs to be manually checked.

ཡིན་/v.fut.v.pres.yin ལོ་/cv.fin: ཡིན་ (209) → v.fut.v.pres.yin - because of the lack of sandhi in the final particle “to be”

ཡིན་/v.past.yin ལོ་/cv.fin: ཡིན་ → v.past.yin - because of the sandhi in the final particle starting with d-

ཡིན་ → v.past.yin

ཡིན་པ་ (41) → n.v.fut.n.v.pres.yin - alternative form ཡིན་པ་ “to be”

ཡིན་པ་ → n.v.past.yin

ཡིན་ལྟགས་ → n.v.fut.n.v.pres.yinlugs “as it is”

ཡོང་ (41) → v.invar.yong “will, to come”

ཡོང་པ་ → n.v.invar.yong “will, to come”

ཡོད་ (98) → v.invar.yod “to exist, to have”

ཡོད་ → v.invar.yod “to have, to exist”

ཡོད་པ་ → n.v.invar.yod “to have, to exist”

རན་ (7) v.invar.ran “to be the time or right moment, to be proper”

རན་/v.past.ran ལོ་/cv.fin: རན་ → v.past.ran - because of the sandhi in the final particle starting with d- ; - རན་/v.past is attested as a past form - this is why རན་ is v.invar.ran and not v.fut.v.pres.ran as done for verbs like yin/yind and min/mind.

རན་ → v.past.ran (ipv)

རན་པ་ (2) → n.v.invar.ran “to be the time or right moment, to be proper”

རན་པ་ → n.v.past.ran (ipv)

རེད་ → v.invar.red “to be”

རེད་པ་ → n.v.invar.red “to be” - alternative form རེད་པ་

རྒྱ་ → v.invar.rgyu “to cause; [following a verb, indicates]: to be done”

རྒྱ་པ་ → n.v.invar.rgyu to cause; [following a verb, indicates]: to be done”

ལགས་ (116) → v.invar.lags “to be” (honorific)

ལགས་པ་ (18) → n.v.invar.lags “to be” (honorific)

ཤེས་ (23) → v.invar.shes “to be able, to be possible, can”

ཤེས་པ་ (35) → n.v.invar.shes “to be able, to be possible, can”

ཤོག་ (56) → v.invar.shog “may it be” - particle indicating the optative

ཤོག་/v.ipv.ong ཅིག་/cv.ipv: note that ཤོག་ is generally regarded as the imperative of འོང་ “to come”, but historically the imperative of གཤེགས་ “to go away, to leave”; when shog is not followed by cv.ipv it can be v.invar.shog or v.ipv.ong. This needs to be manually checked.

ཤོག་པ་ → n.v.invar.shog “may it be”

སྲིད་ (14) → v.invar.srid “to be possible, to be able”

4. Sentence segmentation

Since we cannot rely on punctuation in Tibetan, we have to create clear protocols for sentence segmentation. We follow these basic principles:

1. Sentences must have a matrix verb (unless they are copular clauses with dropped copulas);
2. When in doubt, go for shorter sentences as they are easier to work with in a corpus

- and in any downstream NLP tasks;
- Sentence boundaries do not necessarily reflect linguistic reality but should be consistently annotated;
 - Direct speech is regarded as a separate sentence in the corpus.

4.1 Protocols for <utt>

We summarise our detailed protocols for adding utterance boundaries "<utt>" in the following table, which tells when to insert a sentence boundary, marked by <utt> and when to make sure there is NO sentence boundary. Annotators should be aware that these protocols have been automated and implemented in the POS-tagging script only partially, so along with the word segmentation and POS tags, these utterance boundaries should be double-checked and corrected manually. Examples of each scenario with and without utterance boundaries are added and explained in sections 4.2 and 4.3.

Insert <utt> to create sentence boundary:	Delete/double-check NO <utt>:
After cv.fin or case.fin (+ punc/line.number/page.number)	After cv.ela
After cv.ass (+ punc/line.number/page.number) OR case.ass if following an n.v.*	After cv.all
After v.* (+ line.number/page.number) + punc	After cv.abl
Before AND after direct speech including after case.nare and after cv.ques or case.ques	After cv.loc if conditional
After cv.ipv (+ punc/line.number/page.number) (marking imperatives) case.ipv if it's after a n.v.*	After relative clauses
Before "resumptive" དེ (not དེན)	After cv.odd
If n.v.* is the matrix verb, <utt> can follow (but this is very rare in Old Tibetan and still quite rare in CTib)	After cv.agn
After cv.sem or case.sem	No utterance boundary when there is a verbal complex with cv.sem
After cv.impf or case.impf	After cv.are
After cv.loc in cases after བསམས་ where བསམས་ན is introducing direct speech/thought 'in thinking'	

4.2 Insert sentence boundaries

We segment sentences in the cases outlined below. If there is a [| shad](#) or any other form of punctuation, the sentence boundary marked by "<utt>" follows the punctuation marker(s). Note that these punctuation markers are often, but not always there. Even if they are not

there, we follow the sentence segmentation protocols outlined in this section for consistency.

After cv.fin or case.fin

Sentence-final particles are the clearest markers of utterance boundaries in Tibetan. Whenever we find such markers, whether they're tagged as cv.fin or case.fin, we add an utterance boundary, as shown in (1) and (2). Most of the time these sentence-final particles will be followed by a single or double *shad*, in which case the <utt> marker follows that.

(1) མཚོན་ གྱི་ ཚར་པ་ སལ་ རྣམ། མི་ དང་ སྤྱི་ ལུ་ དམག་ ཀྱང་ སལ་ཚེ་ ར་ བཀུམ་ མོ། <utt>
(Ramayana)

- (2)
- ཡང་ adv.proclausal
 - ན་ case.loc
 - ཞི་ cl.top
 - མི་ n.count
 - འདི་ d.dem
 - འི་ case.gen
 - རྒྱུ་མ་ n.count
 - མངའ་བུད་ n.count
 - ཤིན་ adv.intense
 - དུ་ cv.term
 - མཛེས་ v.invar
 - ཤིང་ cv.impf
 - བཟང་མོ་ n.count
 - ཞིག་ d.indef
 - མོ། case.fin
 - ། punc
 - <utt>

After cv.ass

When the associative marker follows verbs and is thus tagged as cv.ass, this usually indicates two main clauses are coordinated. Since དང/cv.ass is used a lot it would be impractical for parsing and other downstream NLP tasks to consider these two (or often more) main clauses as one sentence in the corpus. Therefore, we consistently add an utterance boundary after དང/cv.ass as shown in (3) and (4):

(3) མཚེད་གཉིས་ཕྱར་གཤེགས་ཤིག་དང་། <utt> བདག་དོན་ཞིག་གཉེར་དེ། སྤྲོད་བཞིན་པར་
མཚོའོ། (MB D 139v2, Bialek 2022 p.146)

(4) འོ་གསུམ་ལོན་པ་དང་། <utt> སྤྱི་བུ་ ང་རྒྱལ་མེས་དཔལ་བཟླར་ཕྱིན་པས།
(GLR 23r4, Bialek 2022 p.149)

After v.*

Since Tibetan is a head-final language, finite verbs appear at the end of main clauses. If there are no sentence-final or similar particles to indicate the end of a sentence, the verb itself is a clear sign that this is the end of a main clause. We therefore insert utterance boundaries after verbs (tagged v.pres, v.past, etc.).

(5) བདག་ ལ་ བྱམས་པ་ རྩོད་ ལས་ གཞན་ མི་ བལྟགས་ | <utt> (Ramayana)

Before AND after direct speech

Direct and indirect speech are notoriously difficult in Tibetan. Often, the beginning and or end of direct speech is marked with a verb ("he said, he asked"), a shortened derivative thereof or a quotative particle. To facilitate future research on (in)direct speech, we create separate sentences for both the clause in (in)direct speech *and* the verb or particle that indicates the (in)direct speech. Note that this will superficially lead to more sentences in the corpus, but since there are separate syntactic labels for each of these clauses (see parsing manual), this should not create any issues when retrieving statistics based on number of sentences in the corpus, as they easily be included or filtered out as necessary.

Sometimes, (in)direct speech can contain more than one main clause. In those cases each main clause in the (in)direct speech will be segmented as a separate sentence following the usual protocols.

Note that this means that the quotative particle should NOT be included in the last main clause of direct speech, as shown in the examples below. Note that the direct speech itself is in red. In examples (6), (7) and (8) we show only the beginning and the end of the direct speech.

Before direct speech:

(6) ལྟ་མོ་ ས་ ལློས་པ་ | <utt> གྱི་ བྱད་ བྱད་མེད་ དགི་ ས་ ལློས་པ་ ལ་ ལེགས་པ་ ར་ ལྱུར་པ་ ག་ ལ་ ཡོད་ །། <utt> (Ramayana)

After direct speech:

(7) དཔལ་ བརྗོད་ འཕུལ་ གྱི་ བསྟེན་ གྲོགས་ ལྟ་མོ་ འདི་ | རྩོད་ ལ་ འཚམ་ <utt> ཞེས་ །། <utt> (Ramayana)

(8) དབེན་བ་ འི་ གནས་ ན་ | ལྟ་ འི་ དྲང་སྲོང་ མཇེད་པ་ ལ་ ཇི་ ཡང་ མི་ དགོས་ མོད་ གྱི་ །། སེམས་ཅན་ བསོད་ནམས་ ཐོབ་པ་ ར་ བྱ་བ་ འི་ ཕྱི་ ར་ །། ལྷན་བ་ ར་ ལྟོབས་པ་ འི་ ལོར་ ལྷང་ འོ་ <utt> ཞེས་ བྱས་ སོ་ །། <utt> (Ramayana)

After case.nare

Direct speech can also be indicated in other ways, for example with the particle རྗེ/case.nare. To be consistent with the above rules concerning direct speech, we also insert utterance boundaries after རྗེ/case.nare, as shown in (9). Note again that the direct speech might end without the quotative particle ཞེས as in this example - here we only have ལྷ་སྐོ་ “said”):

(9) ལྷ་ རྗེ་ ལུ་ རྣམས་ རྗེ་ | <utt> རེད་ མ་ཉ་དེ་བ་ རྗེ་ དངོས་གྲུབ་ འདོད་པ་ ར་ ཟད་ གྱི་ | རལ་པ་ ལུད་ གྱི་ རལ་པ་ ལུད་ གྱི་ དངོས་གྲུབ་ མི་ འདོད་ ཆེས་ <utt> ལྷ་སྐོ་ སོ།། <utt> (Ramayana)

After cv.ques and case.ques

In line with our other protocols regarding direct speech, we also insert utterance boundaries after question particles tagged as cv.ques, shown in (10) or case.ques (not following a verb), shown in (11).

(10) ལྷ་ རྗེ་ དྲུང་སློང་ ལ་ གསོལ་པ་ གྱི་ <utt>
 བརྗེ་ ར་ དགོངས་ | ལུས་པ་ ས་ འབྲུལ་བ་ བཞེས་ ལགས་ སམ་ <utt>
 ཞེས་ ལུས་པ་ དང་ གྱི་ <utt> (Ramayana)

(11)

- བདག་ p.pers
- དེ་ d.dem
- ལ་ case.all
- རྒྱུ་ཟད་ adv.intense
- ཙམ་ d.tsam
- མི་ neg
- དགའ་བ་ n.v.fut.n.v.pres
- འམ་ case.ques
- <utt>
- འཁོན་ v.fut.v.pres
- དུ་ cv.term
- འཛིན་པ་ n.v.pres
- མེད་ v.invar.med
- དོ་ cv.fin
- | punc
- <utt>

After cv.ipv

Again, in line with our protocols regarding (in)direct speech, utterance boundaries should also be added after imperative converbs tagged cv.ipv.

(12) ལྷ་མོ་ རང་ ར་ དཀོན་པ་ འདི་ བཞེས་ འཇིག་ <utt> ཆེས་ དང་ གསོལ་པ་ །། <utt>
(Ramayana)

Before "resumptive" དེ (not དེ་ན)

Sometimes the demonstrative དེ is not used as a modifier but as something that resembles a resumptive pronoun. These "resumptives" come at the start of a sentence, which is why we insert an utterance boundary before དེ in those cases. An example is shown in (13):

(13) <utt> དེ་ནས་བྲག་སྒྲིན་མོ་ལངས་ཏེ། <utt> (GLR 22r6, Bialek 2022 p.118)

If n.v.* is the matrix verb

There are some cases of verbal nouns acting as main clause/matrix verbs. In those cases, we treat them like any other matrix verb and insert an utterance boundary after n.v.* (plus possible punctuation). These cases are very rare in Old Tibetan and still rare in Classical Tibetan, especially in the earlier period.

After cv.sem

Semi-final particles are often used to combine two (or more) clauses that could each be considered matrix clauses. To be consistent and pragmatic (i.e. avoiding very long sentences in annotated corpora), when two or more entire clauses are combined we always insert an utterance boundary after a semi-final particle, as shown in (14).

(14) འོང་སྤྱོད་ ཆེ་བ་ ལས་ །། ལྷ་ རྣམས་ གྱིས་ ལྷོ་ བགྱིས་ ཏེ། | <utt> རྣམ་ཐོས་ གྱི་ སྤྲུམ་ གྱིས་ །།
འགྲུང་ གཅིག་ མེད་པ་ ར་ ལ་ བཏག་ བཅུལ་ བཅད་ དེ། །། <utt> མེད་པ་ ར་ བྱས་ རྣས་ ཡུལ་
ཡང་ ལྷ་ དང་ མི་ ས་ བཀའ་ རོ་ །། <utt> (Ramayana)

There are also cases where there is only one verb after cv.sem. These cases are case it's more like a verbal complex or cases of multiple, concatenated verbs. In those cases, we do not add an utterance boundary after cv.sem, as shown in (15):

(15) ལྷ་དུ་བྱིན་ཏེ་བཞུགས་ན། "When (ན -na) [Vālin's wife] drew near, taking another look,"
(Rama A 204-207)

After cv.impf or case.impf

Imperfective converbs and case markers often behave in a similar way as semi-final particles: even though they can technically indicate subordination, they can also combine two (seemingly) matrix clauses, in which case sentences would get very long. For practical purposes, we therefore treat them in the same way as semi-final particles in the annotated corpus and thus add an utterance boundary after cv/case.impf as shown in (16) and (17):

(16) ལྷ་ མི་ གང་ གིས་ གུང་ མི་ ཐུབ་པ་ ལས་ །། སྒྲིན་པོ་ འི་ འཁོར་ མང་པོ་ །། ཡུལ་ འདི་ ར་

འཕགས་པ་ ར་ རྒྱུད་ ཅིང་ <utt> འོང་སྤྱོད་ ཆེ་བ་ ལས །། ལྟ་ རྣམས་ ཀྱིས་ ལྟོ་ བགྱིས་ ཏེ་ ། <utt>

(17)

རྩ་མཚམས་མ་ n.prop
 རི་ case.gen
 ལྷ་ n.count
 ལྷུ་ num.card
 ལྷུ་ num.card
 ལྷ་ num.card
 གཉེན་པོ་ num.card
 རེ་ d.dem
 རྒྱུ་ cl.top
 གཞིན་ n.count
 རྒྱུ་ case.impf
 <utt>
 དར་ v.invar
 ལ་ cv.all
 བབ་ v.fut.v.past
 ལྟེ་ cv.sem
 ། punc
 <utt>

After cv.loc

Following our protocols for (in)direct speech, in cases after བསམས་ where བསམས་ན་ is introducing direct speech/thought 'in thinking', we add an utterance boundary as well:

(18) ཚོམ་སུ་ ར་ འདུག་པ་ གཅིག་ ལུང་ ཏུ་ བཞག་པ་ རེ་ རྒྱུས་ རས །། བསམས་ ར་ །། <utt>
 ཡུལ་མི་ རྒྱུ་ཚོས་ ཀྱུན་ ལ་ །། ་ ས་མ་ དང་ གཉེན་འདུན་ ཏུ་ བཅས་པ་ ཤེ་ དག་ ར་ །། <utt> ང་
 རི་ ས་མ་ དང་ གཉེན་འདུན་ ལོ་གར་ རོང་ <utt>

"He grew up and thought: 'All the neighbours without exception in the land have parents and relatives. Where did my parents and relatives go?'" (Ramayana)

4.3 No sentence boundaries after:

To be very clear about how to segment sentences, in this section we furthermore highlight cases when NO sentence boundaries are added, i.e. when the utterance should NOT be split/segmented into multiple utterances. Most of these cases contain subordinate clauses that do not have matrix verb, but instead, contain a converb linking the subordinate verb to the main clause.

After cv.agn

The agentive converb is often used for causative clauses. Since this is clearly introducing a subordinate clause, we do NOT add an utterance boundary after cv.agn.

(19)

ང་ p.pers
མི་ neg
ཉན་ v.fut.v.pres
ཀྱིས་ cv.agn
ཚོད་ p.pers
ངང་ case.ass
ཚོ་གྲག་ n.count
དུ་ case.term
བྱ་ v.fut.byed
དགོས་ v.invar.dgos
སོ་ cv.fin
། punc
<utt>

After cv.ela

The elative converb is often used for temporal subordinate clauses and can be translated with "after..." or "since...". Since this is clearly introducing a subordinate clause, we do NOT add an utterance boundary after cv.ela.

(20)

ལྟམ་ n.count
ཀྱིས་ case.agn
ད་ adv.temp
ང་ p.pers
ས་ case.agn
གྲ་མ་ n.count
ལ་ case.all
ལྷན་ v.past
ནས་ cv.ela
ཚོས་ n.count
ཡོང་ v.invar.yong
རང་ p.refl
ཡོང་བ་ n.v.invar.yong
ར་ case.term
བྱ་ v.fut.byed
སོ་ cv.fin
། punc
<utt>

After cv.all

The allative (also known as the dative) converb can introduce subordinate clauses with a temporal meaning, e.g. "during..." or "after...". In those cases the allative marker functions

as a subordinate conjunction and we therefore do NOT insert an utterance boundary after it.

(21)

ཇེས་ n.count
ཤིག་ d.indef
ཕྱོད་ v.ipv
ལ་ cv.all
ལས་ n.count
བྱེད་པ་ n.v.pres.byed
ལྟ་ n.rel
ར་ case.term
བྱིས་ v.ipv.bgyid
ཤིག་ cv.ipv
གསུང་ v.invar
། punc
<utt>

After cv.abl

Just like the elative and allative, the ablative can be used as a 'converb' to introduce a temporal subordinate clause.

(22)

ཚེས་ n.count
འདི་ d.dem
རྒྱ་ n.count
དང་ case.ass
བཅས་ v.invar
ལས་ cv.abl
བྱུང་ v.past.byung
། punc
<utt>

After cv.loc if conditional

The locative marker ན་ introduces conditional clauses and can usually be translated as 'if'. We do not insert utterance boundaries here, because these are subordinate clauses.

(23)

རྒྱུང་ n.count
བཏོན་ v.past
ན་ cv.loc
འཆི་བ་ n.v.fut.n.v.pres
ལས་ case.abl
འོས་ n.count
མེད་ v.invar.med

| punc
<utt>

After relative clauses

Relative clauses are usually introduced by verbal nouns followed by a genitive marker. Relative clauses are subordinate clauses and therefore we do NOT add an utterance boundary between the relative and the main clause.

(24)

ལྷ་མ་ n.count
ཅེ་གསུང་ n.count
ལྷ་བཟུང་བ་ n.v.pres
ལྷ་ case.gen
ལྷ་སྐྱེས་ལུ་ n.count
ལོ་མཚར་ adj
མ་ v.pres
སྐྱེས་ v.invar
| punc
<utt>

After cv.odd

We also do NOT add utterance boundaries after the cv.odd:

(25)

(...)
དང་ case.ass
ལྷ་མ་ n.count
ལྷ་ case.gen
མ་ n.count
ལྷ་བྱང་ v.past.byung
མ་ cv.odd
མ་ v.invar
ལྷ་མ་ cv.impf
ལོ་མཚར་མ་ n.v.past
མ་ case.agn
| punc
<utt>

After verbal complex with cv.sem

Semi-final particles often conjoin two clauses that could be considered main clauses, in which case we add utterance boundaries. However, sometimes there is only one verb after cv.sem, in which case it's more like a verbal complex and there should not be any utterance boundary.

(26) ལྷོ་ལྷོ་ལྷོ་ཏེ་བལྟས་ན། "When (ན་ -na) [Vālin's wife] drew near, taking another look,
(Rama A 204-207)

After cv.are

We do not insert utterance boundaries after cv.are

(27)

ལྷོ་ p.pers
སྲུ་ p.interrog
ཞིག་ d.indef
འདི་ d.dem
ལ་ case.all
མ་ neg
རྟེན་ v.pres
ཤིག་ cv.ipv
ལོ་ལོ་ p.pers
འི་ case.gen
ལྷོ་ n.count
འོངས་ v.past.ong
ནས་ cv.ela
གཞོན་པ་ n.v.invar
ར་ case.term
ལྷོ་ v.past.gyur
ཏེ་ cv.are
ལྷོ་མ་ n.count
ལ་ case.all
སྐྱེས་པ་ n.v.past
། punc
<utt>